

KeyCLIM final report April 2019 - September 2023

Coordination: Norwegian Meteorological Institute
Michael Schulz, Mats Bentsen, Ada Gjermundsen, Dennis Booge,
Andreas Born, Marte Sofie Buraas, Rachael Byrom, Massimo Cassiani,
Richard Davy, Jens Debernard, Sabine Eckhardt, Chuncheng Guo, Heiko
Goelzer, Lise Seland Graff, Konstanze Haubner, Yanchun He, Øivind
Hodnebrog, Stefan Hofer, Mehmet Ilicak, Pål Erik Isachsen, Petra
Langebroek, Kirstin Krüger, Zachary McGraw, Clio Michel, Augustin
Mortier, Gunnar Myhre, Aleksi Nummelin, Dirk Olivié, Stephen Outten,
Birgit Quack, Marit Sandstad, Jörg Schwinger, Jonah Shaw, Asgeir
Sorteberg, Birthe M. Steensen, Trude Storelvmo, Tove Svendby, Andrea
Rosenfeld, Jerry Tjiputra, Thomas Toniazzo

MET Norway, NORCE, NERSC, UiB, UiO, CICERO, NILU

NFR project No. 295046

8 December 2023

Summary

The KeyCLIM project has created a wealth of new knowledge on the importance of coupled processes for the understanding of climate evolution, with some emphasis on a key region of interest, the Arctic and northern high latitudes.

KeyCLIM has resulted already in several important publications comprising those on the aerosol historical forcing (Quaas et al. 2022, Smith et al. 2021), an analysis of biogeochemical feedbacks (Thornhill et al. 2021a), ocean circulation impact on climate sensitivity (Gjermundsen et al. 2021), interactions between North Atlantic Ocean circulation and climate change (Madan et al. 2023), atmospheric rivers and extreme precipitation (Michel et al. 2021), reconstruction of daily Norwegian stream flow from large scale models (Hagen et al. 2023), transport through oceanic Arctic gateways (Shu et al. 2023), maintenance of energy consistency and energy conservation in CMIP-class models of the atmosphere (Lauritzen et al. 2022), an extensive analysis of NorESMs cloud phase representation in the Arctic (Shaw et al. 2022) and an analysis of air-sea-exchange of DMS in CMIP6 models (Bock et al. 2021).

Several other major findings are currently in preparation for peer-reviewed publication based on KeyCLIM NorESM simulations. Among these a) the quantification and localization of heat and moisture transport into the Arctic; b) an analysis of regional circulation patterns; c) an analysis of the Greenland surface mass balance complemented by a study of the interaction of a dynamic Greenland ice sheet with climate; d) a joint study on the sensitivity of winter Arctic amplification on improved NorESM component parameterisations, see below; e) the impact of marine BrF emissions on atmospheric chemistry, including ozone burdens, accounting for a future ice-free Arctic ocean; f) a study on possibly more frequent abrupt marine environmental changes in the future; g) as well as several planned papers to document and evaluate the KeyCLIM NorESM model improvements.

Among the new and most prominent NorESM2 developments within KeyCLIM are an interactive land ice component for Greenland, a high-resolution ocean version, the possibility to switch between hybrid (z-density) and sigma (density) ocean vertical grids, a more realistic mixed phase cloud parameterisation, a revised heat conductivity of snow on sea ice, a rather complex gas-phase chemistry in both the troposphere and stratosphere, an improved air-sea-exchange coupling of bromoform between the ocean and atmosphere and an enhanced parameterisation of mesoscale eddies in the ocean.

Based on these developments, most of the originally planned KeyCLIM sensitivity experiments have been completed for joint analysis. Experiments were dedicated to study an improved heat flux for snow covered sea ice areas, a revised ocean eddy diffusivity, an interactive Greenland ice sheet, the revised ice-cloud microphysics, a complex chemistry including bromoform, volcanic aerosols and ozone and a much reduced anthropogenic forcing by aerosols. The sensitivity experiments all demonstrate enhanced future Arctic warming compared to the CMIP6 reference experiment. The amplitude of the additional warming moreover varies considerably, with the difference between the experiment with the strongest and weakest warming reaching 8.6 K by the end of the 21st Century. Surface temperature decomposition reveals that the warming is dominated by changes in clouds, longwave clear-sky fluxes, surface heat fluxes, and ocean heat storage. We also identify an emergent constraint, linking changes in Arctic surface temperatures to changes in ocean heat fluxes and to changes in sea-ice area.

The new development will contribute to a new updated version NorESM2.3 to be released in early 2024, a version which is important to prepare for a comprehensive upgrade of NorESM for CMIP7. Model simulation results are currently in the process of being archived utilising the Norwegian Research Archive. Along the project timeline KeyCLIM organised several workshops to disseminate progress on model development and major results, among these one workshop on "Constraining model uncertainty in climate sensitivity" and one on "Precipitation trends in Nordic regions". Updates and news are kept on the website for the KeyCLIM project; <https://keyclim.met.no>.

Contents

WP1 Analysis of forcing, feedbacks and circulation changes in CMIP6 and NorESM	4
1.1 Main objectives and goals	4
1.2 Summary and scientific highlights	4
1.3 Major results	4
1.4 Deliverables	11
WP2 Analysis of the hydrological cycle and energy balance in CMIP6 and NorESM	11
2.1 Main objectives and goals	11
2.2 Summary and scientific highlights	12
2.3 Major results	12
2.4 Deliverables	16
WP3 Controls on surface warming in the Arctic by unresolved coupled turbulent transport	16
3.1 Main objectives and goals	16
3.2 Summary and scientific highlights	17
3.3 Major results	17
3.4 Deliverables	24
WP4 Feedbacks involving clouds and the cryosphere	25
4.1 Main objectives and goals	25
4.2 Summary and scientific highlights	25
4.3 Major results	25
4.4 Deliverables	29
WP5 Biogeochemical processes and their gas and aerosol	29
5.1 Main objectives and goals	29
5.2 Summary and scientific highlights	30
5.3 Major results	30
5.4 Deliverables	36
WP6 Assessment of model enhancements through coordinated Earth system experiments	37
6.1 Main objectives and goals	37
6.2 Summary and scientific highlights	37
6.3 Major results	39
6.3.1 Experiments	39
6.3.2 Combined results	40
6.4 Deliverables	41
WP7 Analysis of irreversible climate change with the enhanced NorESM	42
7.1 Main objectives and goals	42
7.2 Summary and scientific highlights	42
7.3 Major results	43
7.4 Deliverables	47
WP8 Coordination of KeyCLIM	47
8.1 Main objectives and goals	47
8.2 Major results	48
8.3 Deliverables	49

WP1 Analysis of forcing, feedbacks and circulation changes in CMIP6 and NorESM

WP leaders: Gunnar Myhre (CICERO), Richard Davy (NERSC)

Contributing persons: Rachael Byrom (CICERO), Gunnar Myhre (CICERO), Richard Davy (NERSC), Stephen Outten (NERSC), Dirk Olivié (MET), Ada Gjermundsen (MET), Michael Schulz (MET).

1.1 Main objectives and goals

Understand key physical processes for climate change and diversity in their representation in multi-model climate simulations on a global scale and over the key region for KeyCLIM. Secondary: (1) Quantify forcing in terms of effective radiative forcing, quantify climate feedbacks, and quantify circulation changes; (2) Establish bias and deficiencies in NorESM in comparison to CMIP6 model ensemble.

1.2 Summary and scientific highlights

Significant progress has been made in understanding and evaluating the radiative forcing and the climate feedbacks in NorESM. (1) The radiative forcing and its components have been characterised and quantified using a considerable number of sensitivity experiments. (2) We show how fundamental differences in the SO circulation and redistribution of ocean heat uptake control the SO cloud response, ultimately delaying the global surface warming in NorESM2 by several centuries in comparison to other CMIP6 models with more pronounced warming. This study resulted in a publication in Nature Geosciences.

1.3 Major results

Task 1.1: Quantification of climate forcing

Significant progress has been made in understanding and evaluating the radiative forcing in NorESM. Through dedicated NorESM2 model simulations to the CMIP6 model intercomparison projects (MIPs) RFMIP and AerChemMIP the effective radiative forcing (ERF) has been quantified for the anthropogenic climate drivers. This includes CO₂, the combination of all well-mixed greenhouse gases, ozone, aerosols and land use change. The aerosol forcing has been diagnosed and NorESM2 and other CMIP6 models show in accordance with observations a reversal of the aerosol effect from a cooling effect prior to 2000 to contributing to a warming after 2000.

The KeyCLIM project made considerable progress in characterising the forcing of climate, through a number of sensitivity simulations. ERF for various climate drivers has been diagnosed in NorESM2-LM for the historical period. For this purpose, the standard RFMIP simulations piClim-histall, piClim-histaer, and piClim-histGHG (Pincus et al. 2016) have been complemented with simulations piClim-histLU (only land use change), piClim-histO3 (only ozone change), piClim-histoxid (only oxidants change), and piClim-histaeroxid (only aerosol emissions and oxidants change). Figure 1.3.1 shows the top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) radiative imbalance in the various simulations. The differences with the piClim-control simulation (black line) can be interpreted as the ERF. The forcing from GHG (blue curve) increases steadily over the historical period reaching almost $+3 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ at the end of the period. The aerosol forcing (turquoise line) is strongly negative and reaches a minimum value in the period 1970–2000 of around -1.5 W m^{-2} , which is stronger than the CMIP6 average (Smith et al. 2021). NorESM2-LM also shows a very modest recovery of the aerosol forcing in the latest decades, but it is weaker than the CMIP6 average. The changing atmospheric oxidant levels (dark green line) over the historical period leads to a small but non-negligible positive ERF (Karsen et al. 2018). Modifying aerosols and oxidants simultaneously (purple line) leads however to a forcing very similar to changing aerosols alone. The contributions from ozone (sea green line) and LU change (brown line) are positive and around $+0.2$ to 0.3 W m^{-2} at the end of the historical period. The positive forcing from land use is opposed to what most CMIP6 models show (Smith et al. 2020a) and related to the decreasing biogenic isoprene and monoterpene emissions over the historical period in NorESM2-LM. The impact of volcanic eruptions is clearly visible in the piClim-histall and piClim-histnat (light green line) simulations. Note on the offset in the reference simulation: the control simulation (piClim) shows an offset of around 0.9 W m^{-2} , although the prescribed SSTs were obtained from the fully coupled piControl simulation which was in equilibrium. This offset is probably caused by reduced near-surface wind-speeds in the fixed-SST simulation leading to lower natural aerosol (precursor) emissions (DMS, ocean POM, dust and sea-salt), and differences in

the description of sea ice. In the fixed-SST simulation, sea ice is always assumed to have a thickness of 1 m, whereas it is variable in the fully-coupled simulations.

Figure 1.3.1: Historical ERF diagnosed as TOA imbalanced in fixed-SST simulations in NorESM2-LM. For the historical simulations the lines shown are the ensemble-mean of three members. As a reference is also shown the long-term averaged TOA imbalance in the piClim-control reference simulation (black line).

The historical aerosol forcing was diagnosed in 11 of the CMIP6 models including NorESM2-LM (Smith et al. 2020a). Figure 1.3.2 shows the time evolution of the aerosol forcing with NorESM2-LM among the models with the strongest aerosol forcing. The spread in the aerosol forcing is large, but the evolution is more similar with a gradual strengthening from 1850 to 1950 and rather strong strengthening until 1980 and thereafter a flat or weakening up to 2014. In all models including a scenario for simulation after 2014 show a clear weakening in the aerosol forcing. Observations clearly indicate that a reversal of the aerosol effect is occurring (Quaas et al. 2022).

Figure 1.3.2: CMIP6 diagnosed net aerosol effective radiative forcing relative to an 1850 climatology. Individual years are shown in dots with an 11 yr Savitzky-Golay smoothing filter applied to show solid lines. The black point and line represents the 17-model mean and range from Smith et al. 2020a for 1850–2014, which did not include E3SM-1-0.

Thornhill et al. 2021b derived the ERFs for individual aerosol components which included both the aerosol-radiation interaction and aerosol-cloud interaction. NorESM2 are among the models with strongest positive ERF of BC and strongest negative ERF of SO₂ emissions (leading to sulphate aerosols),

see Figure 1.3.3. The total aerosol ERF is stronger negative in NorESM2 than in the multi-model mean and consistent with findings from Smith et al. 2020a.

Figure 1.3.3: ERF by aerosol precursor emissions for a range of CMIP6 models.

The Earth energy imbalance (EEI) is increasing (Loeb et al. 2021) and the response will be a surface temperature warming. The strengthening in the imbalance is an opportunity to investigate whether a reversal of the aerosol effect (Quaas et al. 2022) has a strong influence. Figure 1.3.4 shows multi-model and multi-member simulations of the EEI trend, including a comparison to satellite data from CERES. The models have been run with aerosols evolving as in available emission inventories and in addition hold constant at the 2000 level. The figure shows that the enhancement in the EEI in the satellite data can only be simulated in the models when aerosol emissions are allowed to evolve as in the current emission inventories. The multi-model mean shows a strengthening of the EEI trend of $0.20 \text{ W m}^{-2}\text{decade}^{-1}$ when the time evolution of aerosol emissions is accounted for (difference between Fig. 1.3.4 a and b), slightly smaller for NorESM2 ($0.16 \text{ W m}^{-2}\text{decade}^{-1}$).

Figure 1.3.4: Earth energy imbalance from satellite data (CERES) (black) and from two climate models during 2002-2019 with aerosols evolving according to emission inventories (left) and kept constant at 2000 level (right).

The models have been compared to MODIS satellite data of aerosol optical depth (AOD), cloud fraction, and liquid water path (Fig. 1.3.5). The models, including NorESM2, generally simulate well the pattern of change in AOD over regions with large anthropogenic aerosol emissions. AOD trends over South America and high northern latitudes are not reproduced by the models, but these changes are likely related to biomass burning emissions, which are based on climatology from year 2015 in the model simulations. The cloud cover shows some interesting changes, and the pattern of changes over ocean from MODIS is generally captured by the models, with NorESM2 showing somewhat stronger magnitudes of the trends than the multi-model mean.

Figure 1.3.5: Aerosol optical depth, cloud effective radius, liquid water path, and cloud fraction from satellite data (MODIS) (upper row) and from CESM2. The middle row show results when aerosols evolving according to emission inventories and lower row when aerosols are kept constant at 2000 level (right).

Smith et al. 2020a calculated the ERF, instantaneous radiative forcing (IRF) and rapid adjustments for anthropogenic climate drivers for 18 CMIP6 models, including NorESM2. Figure 1.3.6 compares the magnitude of ERF, IRF and rapid adjustments in stratospheric and tropospheric temperature due to an abrupt quadrupling of CO₂ relative to pre-industrial (1850) levels. The purple bars display data calculated by NorESM2-MM, with rapid adjustments calculated using the CAM5 radiative kernels (Pendergrass et al. 2018) and with IRF calculated by the Parallel Offline Radiative Transfer (PORT) code (Conley et al. 2013). The green bars display the NorESM2-MM results of (Smith et al. 2020a), whereby adjustments are calculated using the HadGEM3 radiative kernels (Smith et al. 2020b) with IRF diagnosed using the ‘kernel-difference’ method (Smith et al. 2018) where the IRF is estimated as the residual of ERF minus the sum of all adjustments (also including water vapour, surface temperature, surface albedo and clouds).

Whilst both experiments produce a near identical ERF, the magnitude of IRF varies markedly depending on which method is used to calculate it. When calculated directly, PORT estimates an IRF of 5.30 W m^{-2} . When calculated as a residual of ERF and the sum of all adjustments, the IRF magnitude is considerably lower at 4.76 W m^{-2} . This demonstrates the necessity in calculating this forcing directly using an offline version of a model’s own radiative transfer code and highlights the possibility for error in studies that use the kernel-difference method to derive IRF (Byrom et al., in preparations).

Figure 1.3.6: NorESM2-MM 4xCO₂ ERF, IRF and stratospheric (T_{strat}) and tropospheric (T_{trop}) adjustments (purple bars). IRF is calculated using PORT with T_{strat} and T_{trop} diagnosed using CESM-CAM5 radiative kernels. ERF simulations were run for 30 years, with years 6 to 30 used for analysis. Also shown are corresponding NorESM2-MM data from Smith et al. 2020a (green bars), whereby T_{strat} and T_{trop} are calculated using the HadGEM3 radiative kernels, with IRF estimated as the residual of ERF minus the sum of all adjustments.

Task 1.2: Quantification of climate feedbacks

In the last year report, it was described the important finding of how fundamental differences in the Southern Ocean circulation and redistribution of ocean heat uptake control the Southern Ocean cloud response, ultimately delaying the global surface warming in NorESM2 by several centuries in comparison to other CMIP6 models with more pronounced warming. The study resulted in a publication in Nature Geosciences; Gjermundsen et al. 2021.

90% of the excess heat in the atmosphere is taken up by the Southern Ocean. How that heat is removed from the upper ocean and into the deep ocean has great impact on future warming. Gjermundsen et al. 2021 showed that if the heat taken up by the ocean is mixed into the deep ocean, the surface warming is delayed and the cloud feedback will remain more negative compared to models which tend to keep the heat close to the ocean surface. In particular they investigated the CMIP6 model spread in equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS), which measures how much the near-surface temperature will increase to an instantaneous doubling of the atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration. ECS has become a widely used metric to assess global warming, including the IPCC assessment reports. The Earth System Models participating in CMIP6 exhibit on average a wider range of ECS values compared to CMIP5 (Zelinka et al. 2020). The NorESM model exhibits a low climate sensitivity (2.5 K; Seland et al. 2020), actually among the lowest among the CMIP6 ensemble, in great contrast to CESM which is among the high ECS models, with a 5.2K warming. The different ocean components in the two models trigger initially different cloud feedbacks in those first 150 years generally used for ECS analysis (Gjermundsen et al. 2021). For the same surface temperature increase, NorESM2 and CESM2 exhibit similar feedbacks (Fig. 1.3.7, left). However, the warming and hence the onset of a more positive cloud feedback is delayed in NorESM2 mainly due to fundamental differences in the base state of the ocean components and the redistribution of accessible heat taken up by the Southern Ocean under greenhouse gas-forcing (Fig. 1.3.7). Further, NorESM2, is on multi-centennial time scales a high-ECS model, in particular when the ocean surface waters have warmed enough to trigger a more positive cloud feedbacks in the Southern hemisphere extratropics. The potential for greenhouse gas (GHG)-induced warming in NorESM2 is not fully captured in the first 150 years generally used for ECS analysis, including the assessment reports from the IPCC.

Figure 1.3.7: Left: **a,b**, Time evolution of cloud-cover fraction anomaly averaged south of 35°S for CESM2 (**a**) and NorESM2-LM (**b**) for the first 500 years. **c,d**, SST anomaly for the same region and time as in **a** and **b** for CESM2 (**c**) and NorESM2-LM (**d**). **e,f**, Zonally averaged SW cloud feedback in NorESM2-MM (orange), NorESM2-LM (black) and CESM2 (blue) after 150 years (**e**) and after 500 years in NorESM2-LM (grey) and CESM2 (light blue) (**f**). Also included in **f** is the SW cloud feedback from CESM2 (blue) after 150 years for comparison. Right: **a**, Ocean temperature anomaly averaged south of 50°S in NorESM2-MM (orange), NorESM2-LM (black) and CESM2 (blue) after 150 years and after 500 years in NorESM2-LM (grey) and CESM2 (light blue). **b,c**, Zonally averaged ocean temperature anomaly after 500 years in NorESM2-LM (**b**) and CESM2 (**c**). **d,e**, Changes in eddy-induced MOC (shading) and density (black dashed lines) to abrupt- $4\times\text{CO}_2$ forcing after 150 years in CESM2 (**d**) and NorESM2-LM (**e**). The black arrows indicate the anomalous along-isopycnal transport, and the red contour shows the 1 K warming

NorESM2 was among the CMIP6 models used to estimate the climate feedbacks from aerosols (Thornhill et al. 2021a). Climate feedbacks from dust and DMS were found to be small, see Fig. 1.3.8. Sea salt and biogenic VOC had negative climate feedbacks for model-mean, but especially for biogenic VOC, the model diversity was large.

Task 1.3: Quantification of circulation biases and response to forcing

There has been substantial new findings about circulation biases in our key region and how they change due to natural variability and as a response to changes in external forcing. We created and made use of a novel analysis toolkit for using the Common Basis Function approach which enables a fair comparison of modes of variability found in observations and models. This is based on empirical orthogonal function analysis but rather than comparing modes of variability diagnosed in models and observations, we instead project the modes found in observations into the model anomaly space. This changes the question from "How well do modes of variability in the models compare to those found in observations?" to "How well do models capture observed modes of variability?". This avoids many of the common problems of EOF analysis such as mode swapping, overlapping modes, and arbitrary sign. The python toolkit has been made available on the NERSC github account <https://github.com/nanscenter/CommonBasisFunction>.

Since the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) is the major mode of variability that controls climate variability in our key region of interest (the North Atlantic, Europe, and the European Arctic), we chose to look at slow changes to the NAO as found in the available 20th century reanalyses and compare these to historical simulations from the different versions of NorESM as well as all other available CMIP6 models. While some aspects of the NAO have been widely studied there has been no analysis of the slow changes in the relative magnitude (i.e. the percentage of variance explained) of the NAO and the other modes of variability in the region, the mid-atlantic ridge and Scandinavian blocking patterns. We have discovered that it is only since the 1930s that the NAO has been the dominant mode of variability in this region, and that the relative importance of the NAO has increase by about 60 % since 1930.

Figure 1.3.8: Climate-driven chemistry and aerosol feedbacks in CMIP6 Earth system models. Results redrawn from (Thornhill et al. 2021a) in Fiedler et al. (in review).

This increase in the importance of the NAO is related to a decrease in the relative importance of the Mid-Atlantic ridge which has occurred continuously since the 1920s; and a decrease in the Scandinavian blocking pattern which also saw a decrease since the 1950s (see figure 1.3.9).

These changes to the explained variance are of great significance for low-frequency natural variability in precipitation extremes over Europe, as it has been demonstrated the close link between the NAO pattern and the frequency and intensity of precipitation and precipitation extremes, especially in winter. We investigated which regions in Europe are most affected by each of the first three major modes of variability in the North Atlantic, by determining which timeseries of explained variance best fit the local changes in precipitation over the 20th century (see figure 1.3.10). We clearly see that changes in precipitation over Norway are predominately explained by changes in the positive phase of the NAO, while changes to precipitation over the Mediterranean countries are most closely related to the negative NAO. A proposal has been submitted to the Bjerknes center to continue work connecting these changes in the relative importance of the NAO to changes in the frequency of weather events and precipitation extremes over Europe.

Given the importance of the NAO and its multi-decadal variability is for precipitation in our key region we investigated how well current climate models capture these relationships. We conducted a CBF analysis of 50 CMIP6 models including all NorESM versions to assess how well they capture these slow changes in the explained variance of the different modes of variability and to determine if the changes to these modes are due to a forced response or natural variability. These results were presented in last years report. In brief we found no evidence that the observed changes to the modes of variability are due to a forced response; that the climate models tended to overestimate the variability in the explained variance of the NAO; and that they were also biased towards over-estimating the importance of the NAO. This has important implications for near-term climate prediction as the phase of natural variability in the NAO strongly influences the changes in precipitation and precipitation extremes in Europe. However, this depends upon whether the CMIP6 models' have the same relationship between the modes of variability and precipitation as has been found in the reanalyses. To assess if these models captured this behaviour we conducted the same analysis as presented in 1.3.10) for each of the 50 CMIP6 models. We then checked the percentage of gridpoints in each of the models which agreed with the reanalysis as to which mode of variability best explained local changes to precipitation (1.3.11). There is a startlingly large separation in the results with around 60% of the models having a good agreement with the reanalysis (around 50%) and then 40% of the models have a very poor agreement with the reanalysis (less than 10%). More work is needed to investigate why there is such a band-gap in model agreement with reanalysis and a proposal has been submitted to further investigate this. However, given that the Norwegian Climate Prediction model (NorCPM) is one of those models which does not agree well with the reanalysis it is imperative this is further investigated if the model skill we have seen with NorCPM in the ocean is going to be transferred to skill in predicting changes to precipitation and precipitation extremes over Europe.

Figure 1.3.9: The percentage of variance explained by each of the first three modes of sea level pressure variance in 30 year windows from the ERA and NOAA 20th century reanalyses. The modes correspond to 1. the NAO, 2. the Mid-Atlantic ridge, and 3. the Scandinavian blocking patterns respectively. The insert shows the spatial pattern of the first mode from the years centered around 1920 and 1930 when it was the Mid-Atlantic ridge and the NAO which had the largest explained variance respectively. Results from Outten and Davy 2023.

1.4 Deliverables

- D1.1 Publication on historical ERF and contributions from various climate drivers. This was made available for IPCC AR6 (Smith et al. 2020a Smith et al. 2021 Thornhill et al. 2021b Skeie et al. 2020)
- D1.2 Publication on diversity in climate feedbacks in CMIP6 models in the key region (Thornhill et al. 2021a, Gjermundsen et al. 2021)
- D1.3 Publication on regional circulation patterns, comparing CMIP6 and ERA5 reanalysis (Outten and Davy, 2023, *accepted for Weather and Climate Dynamics Discussions*)

WP2 Analysis of the hydrological cycle and energy balance in CMIP6 and NorESM

WP leaders: Sabine Eckhardt (NILU), Asgeir Sorteberg (UiB)

Contributing persons: Sabine Eckhardt (NILU), Tove Svendby (NILU), Massimo Cassiani (NILU), Asgeir Sorteberg (UiB), Clio Michel (UiB), Chuncheng Guo (NORCE), Heiko Goelzer (NORCE), Petra Langebroek (NORCE), Birthe M. Steensen (CICERO), Marit Sandstad (CICERO), Øivind Hodnebrog (CICERO), Gunnar Myhre (CICERO).

2.1 Main objectives and goals

For capturing the impacts and the mechanism of Arctic Amplification, we analyze the hydrological cycle at the northern latitudes and investigate the pathways for energy import into the Arctic region. For this purpose, data from ECMWF reanalysis projects as well as different versions of NorESM and other

Figure 1.3.10: The mode of variability for which the changes in the explained variance over time best explains the local changes in mean precipitation. Grey colours are shown when there was no significant correlation with any of the modes. Results from Davy et al. 2024 (in prep).

climate models participating in CMIP6 are used. The goal is to quantify the different climate relevant components and document their interannual variability.

2.2 Summary and scientific highlights

The Arctic moisture balance was analyzed using different methods and a connection between all the approaches has been established. We performed a quantitative analysis of energy and moisture fluxes, and trend studies for precipitation events based on an energy balance and on a mechanistic approach through the identification of atmospheric rivers. The analysis shows that the region east of Greenland and the Barents Sea experiences the strongest changes. In most of the analysis NorESM and ECMWF reanalysis show similar patterns for the last decades. In particular, we highlight: A paper on the connection of atmospheric rivers (AR) to extreme precipitation has been published Michel et al., 2021. The impact of atmospheric circulation patterns on flooding occurrence was investigated with the help of machine learning algorithm. The streamflow in catchments has been successfully captured with a multilayer perceptron model Hagen et al., 2021. The manuscript on marine transport is published in Geoscientific Model Development (Shu et al. 2023).

2.3 Major results

Task 2.1: Quantification of heat and moisture transport into the Arctic and their effect on the Arctic climate

A better understanding of the potentially huge impact of moisture transport on Arctic warming is crucial to constrain the large model spread seen in CMIP6 (Rantanen et al. 2022). The Eulerian analysis of heat and moisture transport into the Arctic region showed that the moisture import has maxima in distinct regions, with largest positive energy fluxes (transport into the Arctic) over the Atlantic, Pacific but also a smaller contribution over Eurasia. In order to investigate the source regions which feed those moisture fluxes we performed a Lagrangian analysis based 12 days backward trajectories to identify regions of moisture loss and moisture uptake at the Arctic region above 66N, which corresponds to the latitude where the Eulerian analysis has been performed. While during winter (Fig 2.3.1) ocean areas at the North American east coast end on the eastern Atlantic are a source, in summer the Eurasian and American continents are the areas where moisture uptake takes place. The North Atlantic stormtrack is the most important moisture source. In order to see the changes in a warming climate we calculate the difference between 2020-2030 versus 2040-2050 (Fig. 2.3.1). The zones of increased moisture uptake are not equally distributed. High latitude continental sources increase in summer and in winter source regions strengthen in the Barent sea and western Atlantic. An additional analysis has been performed with the ECMWF ERA-5 reanalysis and show similar features. For estimating the impact of the changes in NorESM simulations having implemented improved parametrizations have been performed. The focus

Figure 1.3.11: The percentage of gridpoints in each of the 50 CMIP6 models that agree with the findings from the ERA5 reanalysis about which mode of variability best explains local changes in precipitation. Results from Davy et al. 2024 (in prep).

of this study is to analyse components leading to Arctic warming and there is a focus on the winter month DJF. All components from ocean energy budget, global circulation, moisture budget and AMOC will be analysed in a holistic way. At the same time comparison to reanalysis data are compared for the historical NorESM simulation Fig. 2.3.2. There is a good match for the historic data across the different analysed parameters. From all the simulations the greatest differences can be seen in the „snow“ and „cloud“ scenarios. In the IWV a moisture increase is seen in the snow scenario, while the cloud scenario shows less moisture increase compared to the other scenarios. The heat and volumn transport through the oceanic Arctic gateways and Arctic liquid freshwater sources and content in CMIP6 has been analysed (Shu et al., 2023). The CMIP6/OMIP intercomparison showed that the models (including NorESM/BLOM) qualitatively agree with the observed variability and change of the gateway volume/heat/salt transport. This is not unexpected, as the OMIP models were forced by the same atmospheric reanalysis. However, large model biases and spread exist in the simulated mean state of hydrography in the vertical direction, especially the warm Atlantic Water layer. The NorESM/BLOM is among the coldest-biased models. This has been a known long-standing issue for NorESM/BLOM, and stresses further need of model development in this region.

Task 2.2: Understanding regional precipitation changes

Trend analyses over the last 30 years (1991-2020) show an increase in precipitation over the arctic for NorESM and reanalysis data ERA-5, and that this increase is especially strong during September and October (Fig 2.3.3). Regional atmospheric energy budget analysis shows that this precipitation change is caused by dry static energy transport and moisture convergence. The largest signals are found in the over Greenland, the Norwegian Sea and the Barents Sea. The increase in precipitation over the arctic between NorESM historical simulations and ERA-5 over the recent years are similar compared to other CMIP6 model simulations, and both models show an increase around the CMIP6 mean. End of the century precipitation changes for ssp370 simulations however show that NorESM have a lower increase compared to the other CMIP6 models, and that there is a large spread between the models. Regional atmospheric energy budget analysis for the CMIP6 models identifies lower dry static heat divergence and sensible heat as the main source for this precipitation difference.

The frequency of atmospheric rivers (ARs) crossing 70°N increases in almost all seasons and all longitudes ((Fig 2.3.4). The largest increase occurs mostly in summer (JJA, red line) and the weakest occurs in winter (DJF, cyan line). However, the results are slightly different when considering a lower latitude (60°N, not shown). The proportion of extreme precipitation events due to ARs seems to increase (up to 30%) by the end of the century compared to the present period over most of a North Atlantic-European-Scandinavian domain with the largest increases found over sea and Northern UK (not shown).

Figure 2.3.1: Regions of moisture uptake (positive values) and loss (negative values) as derived from a Lagrangian analysis performed on NorESM SSP-850 for moisture uptake for summer (upper row) and winter (lower row) for the 90 percentile of high moisture situations in the Arctic. The left panels are for the period 2020-2030, while the right panels for the difference between the decade after 2040 and the decade after 2020.

Michel et al. (2021) identified and analyzed the connection between landfalling atmospheric rivers (ARs) and extreme precipitation in Norway. A clear link was seen in all regions. It was especially clear in western Norway and occurs most often in fall (Fig 2.3.5). A well-defined low-pressure system was found near the AR landfall point in 70% of the cases. When the cyclone is located over the British Isles, as it is typically the case when ARs reach Southeastern Norway, it is associated with cyclonic Rossby wave breaking whereas when the ARs reach more northern regions, anticyclonic wave breaking occurs over Northern Europe. Cyclone-centered composites show that the mean sea level pressure is not significantly different between the eight Norwegian regions and lagrangian air parcel tracking show that moisture uptake mainly occurs over the North Atlantic for the coastal regions with an additional source over Europe for the more eastern and inland regions.

Task 2.3: Hydrological (including Greenland snow) response to large scale decadal atmospheric variability and long-term changes

Previous studies linking large-scale atmospheric circulation and river flow with traditional machine learning techniques have predominantly explored monthly, seasonal or annual streamflow modeling for applications in direct downscaling or hydrological climate-impact studies. In Hagen et al. 2021 we investigate the possibility of estimating daily streamflow directly from large-scale atmospheric circulation using two reanalysis datasets and three machine learning approaches (random forest (RF), support vector machine (SVM) and multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural networks). These are compared to simple multiple-linear regression to assess the role of model complexity (Fig 2.3.6). In all but the smallest, rainfall-driven catchment, the most complex model, MLP showed better skill than the simpler models and was able to predict streamflow in both dominantly snowmelt-driven and rainfall-driven streamflow regimes. The Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) ranged from 0.71 to 0.81, which is very promising. The study provides a nice benchmark for future development of deep learning models for direct downscaling from large-scale atmospheric variables to daily streamflow without the need of calibrated hydrological models. In Hagen et al. 2023 we showed that neural networks fed solely with catchment-specific large-scale atmospheric

Figure 2.3.2: Integrated water vapor [kg m^{-2}] of the ERA-5 data (h) for the period 1985-2022, the NorESM2-MM historical simulation (i) from 1985-2014. Panel a shows the difference between the average of six future scenarios. The differences between the differences of the average and the respective future scenario is shown in panel b-g.

variables from coarse scale reanalysis reconstructed daily streamflow of comparable quality as a calibrated traditional hydrologic model forced with 1×1 km gridded observational based data. The best machine learning model had a median Nash Sutcliffe of 0.78, compared to 0.81 for the traditional hydrological model. However, extreme value analysis suggested that even if the machine learning models in general are very good at simulating daily streamflow directly from atmospheric data, they all have problems with learning the extremes. Figure 2.3.7 shows the typical underestimation of extreme events. The results also indicated that networks that are constructed to better allow information to persist in the network (better memory of lagged information) such as the bidirectional LSTM neural network is performing considerably better than the other models in terms of the extremes.

We have run a series of experiments with NorESM2 including a dynamic Greenland ice sheet model. The runs were performed for two different resolutions of the climate model and cover the pre-industrial, the historical period and projections to year 2100 (2300) under (prolonged) SSP585 forcing. The surface mass balance (SMB) over the Greenland ice sheet for these experiments is calculated using an elevation class method to downscale the relatively coarse surface mass and energy components from the land model to the high-resolution ice sheet grid. Comparison with high-resolution regional climate model simulations and observations (Figure 2.3.8) indicates that NorESM2 produces an SMB over the historical period that captures the large-scale features of the Greenland ice sheet (north-south gradient, high SMB in the south-east, negative SMB in the central west). However, the resulting SMB shows some biases,

Figure 2.3.3: Precipitation trend changes in October for between 1991-2020 for a) NorESM historical with ssp 370 the last 6 years and b) ERA-5 reanalysis data. Shaded regions show where the trend is not statistically significant.

in particular a too high SMB along the margins, which can partially be explained by a cold bias of NorESM2 around the Greenland margins. Coastal precipitation in the southeast is smoothed into the interior and topographically driven precipitation is generally not well resolved due to the relatively coarse resolution of the atmosphere model. The higher resolution model (NorESM2-MM, $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$) slightly improves this situation compared to NorESM2-LM ($2^\circ \times 2^\circ$), in particular the precipitation biases. A publication documenting the coupled climate - ice sheet model is in preparation (D2.7).

2.4 Deliverables

- D2.1 Climatology database of atmospheric heat and moisture transport (completed, will be distributed with a DOI in the publication in D2.2.)
- D2.2 Publication on atmospheric heat and moisture transport into the Arctic (Eckhardt et al., Moisture source regions and transport pathways into the Arctic in a past and future climate, to be submitted to ACP)
- D2.3 Publication on transport through oceanic Arctic gateways (Shu et al., 2023)
- D2.4 Publ. on regional precip. changes and atmospheric energy budget (Myhre et al., in progress)
- D2.5 Publication on regional changes in ARs and extreme precip. (Michel et al. 2021)
- D2.6 Publication on the links of regional floods to large-scale atmospheric flow (Hagen et al., 2021, Hagen et al., 2023)
- D2.7 Publication on the Greenland surface mass balance (Goelzer et al., in progress)

WP3 Controls on surface warming in the Arctic by unresolved coupled turbulent transport

WP leaders: Thomas Toniazzo (NORCE), Mats Bentsen (NORCE)

Contributing persons: Thomas Toniazzo (NORCE), Richard Davy (NERSC), Mats Bentsen (NORCE), Mehmet Ilicak (NORCE), Aleksi Nummelin (NORCE), Pål Erik Isachsen (UiO), Jens Debernard (MET).

3.1 Main objectives and goals

Improve representation of boundary layer processes in NorESM: (1) Explore effects on surface Arctic temperature and stratification associated with coupled ocean and atmosphere boundary-layer processes

Figure 2.3.4: Atmospheric river (AR) frequency change between the future period 2061-2100 and the present-day period 1979-2018 considering ARs crossing the 70°N parallel poleward. At the bottom, blue lines represent the sea and brown lines the land. NorESM2-MM historical and SSP5-8.5 are used here.

in the key region and improve their representation; (2) Explore effects of bottom topography and sea ice in the parameterization of unresolved high latitude ocean eddy transport; (3) Identify and remove numerical modes in the dynamical ocean-sea ice coupling in NorESM.

3.2 Summary and scientific highlights

Work has progressed from the stages of exploration and code development to comprehensive simulations including all or most of the new science, and their evaluation. Some of the previous results carried over, in other cases coupling with other components results in different (and partly unexpected) behaviour. Some of the efforts currently underway are focussed on finding a comprehensive configuration that brings the simulations back to the envelope of acceptable climatologies for scientific studies. In terms of scientific milestones we highlight:

1. Long climate relevant simulations are now possible with the hybrid (p -density) vertical coordinate in BLOM, due to improvements to the essential vertical regridding and remapping, along with adaptation of key physical parameterizations.
2. Co-authoring a leading publication on the problem of maintaining energy consistency and energy conservation in CMIP-class models of the atmosphere, which is a necessary and important step towards the progressive implementation of model formulation changes that improve the current status.
3. Inclusion of an additional length scale, the topographic Rhines scale, is found to capture the reduction in mesoscale eddy diffusivity over sloping topography seen in idealized eddy-resolving simulations.

3.3 Major results

Task 3.1: Coupled boundary-layer processes in the Arctic

a) Setup of ocean/sea ice/atmosphere coupled single column model (SCM) testbed:

The CAM single column model (SCM) is available within the coupled framework but a coupled SCM

Figure 2.3.5: Map displaying Norway divided in eight regions (colors) with the 206 stations used in the study superimposed (blue dots). The red line represents all possible starting points for the detection of landfalling atmospheric rivers. The table to the left shows the percentage of extreme events associated with ARs in each region and the season when this link occurs most often in parenthesis for the period 1979–2018. Regions are indicated by their first letter as displayed in the map legend.

Figure 2.3.6: Example of observed (blue) and reconstructed daily flows from identified drivers by using a MLP neural network using atmospheric data from ERA5 (orange) and ERAI (purple) for a typical snowmelt (left) and rainfed (right) catchment.

case configuration with ocean and ice was abandoned, because no configuration coupled to BLOM and CICE SCM could be made available in useful time. Currently only coupling of CAM-SCM with a slab is available, but its applicability is limited. A single column configuration has eventually been developed for BLOM in standalone configuration and available in the code repository. Within KeyCLIM the BLOM SCM is used for the development of the hybrid vertical coordinate in BLOM, particularly for testing of the new vertical mixing implementation needed for this coordinate.

b) Formulation and discretisation of stable cold PBLs in CLUBB:

1. Extensive experimentation has been carried out with increased vertical resolution both in the PBL and in the free troposphere. In contrast to CESM, this was possible in NorESM without major problems because the resolution-dependence of the convection scheme was already removed in the CMIP6 version of the model. NCAR has adopted our solution since. Results with higher vertical resolution were very encouraging in terms of validation of the simulated atmospheric state, but that was associated with a severe TOA energy imbalance of 5 W/mq which could not be easily tuned. In view of the doubling of the model cost this development is therefore currently frozen. The main successful development for the atmospheric PBL consists in the activation of prognostic

Figure 2.3.7: estimates of 2-, 5-, 10-, 20-, 50-, 100- and 200-year return values for streamflow (Q) in a rain fed (left) and snow fed (right) catchment. Black lines are the observations based on 61 years of data with the 95% and 5% confidence intervals shaded in gray. Blue squares represent the GBRT model, pink crosses represent the MLP network, and orange circles represent the LSTM network.

momentum fluxes in CLUBB (Larson et al. 2019). Initially this led to severe numerical instability which has been diagnosed in KeyCLIM work to stem from the interaction between the PBL physics package and the coupling between the atmosphere and the surface components. The inconsistency has been resolved by numerical iteration between the PBL and the surface stress; the latter is now updated by CAM. The instability has thus been successfully removed enabling prognostic momentum transfer between the atmosphere and the surface. The numerical scheme developed under KeyCLIM has now been imported and become a standard part of more recent versions of CESM (cf <https://github.com/ESCOMP/CAM/issues/342>), and hence of NorESM.

2. This numerical development has led to a reduction of the model's systematic westerly surface-wind bias in the mid-latitudes. See Fig. 3.3.1a. A further development that is currently frozen is the implementation of the Esau (2007) scheme of air-sea exchange enhancement due to occurrence of leads over sea-ice. The implementation was successful and the results of the parameterization are in line with expectation, but its impact on the model simulation is again a severe TOA imbalance that appears very difficult to tune away. All experiments mentioned in this task were performed in a configuration coupled to a slab ocean in order to include first-order thermodynamic coupling effects. They also include an important fix of a severe bug in the cloud scheme (cf WP4) that also has wide-ranging impacts both on the model climatology and on its climate sensitivity. The combined changes in PBL physics and cloud physics leads to a warmer control climate (by about 1C) and a reduced climate sensitivity (also by about 1C per doubling of CO₂). See Fig. 3.3.1a.

c) Refinement of the vertical discretisation and physics in the PBL of BLOM:

BLOM uses near-isopycnic interior layers with the PBL represented by two variable density layers. To allow better vertical resolution in the PBL, a hybrid vertical coordinate has been implemented in BLOM that offers greatly improved flexibility in choosing a suitable vertical discretization. Our choice for the hybrid coordinate in KeyCLIM uses continuous isopycnals in the ocean interior White et al., 2009, that gradually approaches constant pressure levels towards the surface, allowing much improved vertical resolution in the PBL. For the regriding step, the continuous isopycnals approach, as implemented in BLOM, uses a novel approach of gently nudging the layer interfaces towards desired density at each time-step. For the development of a hybrid vertical in BLOM, a standalone Fortran module has been implemented containing routines and data structures for high-order one-dimensional reconstruction and remapping on nonuniform grids based on the approach of White and Adcroft 2008. The reconstruction is currently up to 5th order accurate (3rd order method is default) on nonuniform grids using a compact scheme with various limiting methods implemented to control spurious oscillations and monotonicity. Compared to White and Adcroft 2008 the BLOM implementation has: a novel non-oscillatory limiting method that improves accuracy at smooth extrema, while controlling spurious oscillations near sharp features; refinement of reconstruction boundary conditions; and a robust handling of thin layers. A

Figure 2.3.8: Mean surface mass balance over the period 1960-1989 from a) NorESM2-LM, b) NorESM2-MM and from regional climate model MAR downscaling c) NorESM2-MM and d) ERA reanalysis. All fields are masked to the modelled ice sheet area in NorESM2-MM at the end of year 2014.

comparison of the layer structure with the old BLOM vertical coordinate and the new hybrid coordinate is shown in Fig. 3.3.2.

In contrast to the old vertical coordinate, the hybrid vertical coordinate requires a vertical mixing parameterization suitable for both a well resolved upper ocean and an isopycnic interior. For this purpose we have implemented the K Profile Parameterization KPP (Large et al., 1994), extended with tidal mixing parameterization, by interfacing to the Community Vertical Mixing Project (CVMix; <http://cvmix.github.io>) package. Deviations from the standard KPP are the application of nonlocal distribution of surface momentum flux and that the nonlocal distribution of brine flux from sea-ice freezing has an absorption profile is skewed towards the base of the PBL in BLOM, greatly improving the PBL depth in sea-ice freezing conditions. The KPP parameterization gives insufficient mixing in gravity currents and work remains to handle this in a satisfactory manner.

Key physical parameterizations of BLOM, such as Gent and McWilliams 1990 eddy-induced transport and submesoscale eddy-induced transport in the PBL by Fox-Kemper et al. 2008, has been adapted to work with the hybrid vertical coordinate. Eddy-induced diffusion in the ocean interior occurs primarily along neutral surfaces, on which water parcels are neutrally buoyant. For isopycnic coordinates, layer-wise eddy diffusion is mostly a reasonable approximation to neutral diffusion. With hybrid coordinates, there may be regions where layers are not well-aligned with neutral surfaces. In z -level models this has traditionally been handled using a rotated diffusion operator oriented along the neutral tangent plane. Shao et al. 2020 recently proposed a method for implementing neutral diffusion making use of nonlocal neutral sublayers. This method is now implemented in BLOM and the default option when using hybrid vertical coordinate.

d) Conserving material-energy fluxes between submodels: In-depth analysis of the atmospheric component made it clear that the goal of achieving such conservation to a degree of accuracy significantly better than at present requires extensive changes to the model. In particular, the atmospheric PBL parametrisation is formulated on a different, and incompatible, set of equations to that of the rest of the physics, rendering local conservation within the atmospheric model impossible at present. Our mathematical and physical analysis contributed substantially to a collaborative paper led by NCAR Lauritzen et al., 2022 where the issues associated with energy consistency and conservation are clearly laid out in detail and with some degree of completeness. This paper was made possible by the collaboration between 20 co-authors among the most established scientists in model development and has been highlighted (cf. <https://eos.org/editor-highlights/consistently-closing-the-energy-budget-in-earth-system-models>) as a “benchmark” that will enable improving the representation of energy in the climate system not only in CAM but in the other CMIP-class models as well.

e) Experiments on coupled sensitivity of near-surface SCM processes:

With regard to the SCM set-up, we refer to point a) above. As mentioned in point b) the development activity on an improved atmospheric PBL representation using a flexible prescribed-SST and slab model

Figure 3.3.1: (a) Latitude-height plots of differences in tropospheric temperatures and winds between experiments with increased vertical resolution (“L64”) and/or prognostic PBL momentum fluxes (“CLUBB”). (b) Impact on global-mean temperatures of the combined cloud physics bug fix and the improved PBL turbulence scheme. Red symbols refer to the control simulation (standard NorESM2), blue symbols to the modified model configuration.

configurations resulted, together with bug fixes and adjustment to the parametrisation of mixed-phase cloud, in promising simulations and an expectation to follow up with fully coupled experiments with either or both new atmosphere and ocean PBL representations and explore the model sensitivity to those developments. It turned out that coupling BLOM with the modified atmospheric PBL results in large changes in tropical and extratropical SSTs that lead in particular to a weak surface tropical wind field through an associated Bjerknes feedback. Although a historical integration (1850-2010) was completed with the new atmosphere PBL, after an approximately 100-year-long spin-up phase, a persistent TOA imbalance and associated ocean temperature drift was considered unacceptable in terms of obtaining scientifically valid results from this or similar simulations. In other words a strong need for re-tuning the coupled model was identified and corresponding efforts have been underway. This tuning activity is shared with WP4, since progress has been made there in terms of a physically meaningful adjustment and tuning of mixed-phase cloud which needs to be performed using, and in conjunction with, the updated PBL parametrisations. Currently, parallel experiments are underway, including prescribed-ocean, prescribed-atmosphere, and coupled set-ups. We also took advantage of a tuning exercise underway at the Nansen Centre aimed at reducing mean model biases in the tropical Atlantic, in which we were involved in an advisory role to suggest tuning parameters and value ranges to explore. New developments and parameter tunings for the ocean PBL and associated mixing processes are being explored in parallel. We are using a common experimental test-bed (“sandbox”) that includes all relevant code changes. The aim, within KeyClim, is not to optimise the simulated climatology (as done e.g. for CMIP) but only to obtain a configuration in approximate TOA balance and a reasonable SST and cloud climatology. A summary table of the activities follows.

- 3.1.e.i coupled HIST (1850-2010) with atmosph. PBL completed (with some spin-up)
- 3.1.e.ii initial PI control spin-up integrations with combined atmosph. and ocean PBLs evaluated

Figure 3.3.2: Potential temperature and layer structure in a Pacific section (upper 700 m) in the final month of an OMIP1 forcing cycle (62 years) in simulations using isopycnic (a) and hybrid (b) vertical.

- 3.1.e.iii microphysics iteration tests with WP4 (on prescribed-SST and slab cases)
- 3.1.e.iv tuning tests together with WP4 (6-8 parameters) on prescribed-SST cases, underway
- 3.1.e.v diffusivity perturbation tests on OMIP1 cases, underway
- 3.1.e.vi preparation of “sandbox” for new coupled PI control

f) Assessment of the impact of PBL representations on hydrography and circulation in the key region in AMIP and OMIP sensitivity experiments and in coupled WP6 simulations:

Extensive testing of the hybrid coordinate BLOM has been done using OMIP type simulations (coupled ocean/sea-ice simulations with observation based atmosphere and runoff forcing). These simulations also include iHAMOCC for ocean biogeochemistry. Figs. 3.3.3a and 3.3.3b compares global zonal mean temperature bias after one forcing cycle of the OMIP1 protocol, using isopycnic and hybrid coordinates, respectively. Overall the difference to climatology is on par or reduced in the upper ocean using the hybrid coordinate. The cold bias seen at depth in the Southern Ocean (SO) of the isopycnic simulation is greatly reduced with the new coordinate and the more realistically stratified SO also improves the simulation of biogeochemical tracers in that region. The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) strength of simulations with different vertical coordinates and the OMIP1 and OMP2 forcing protocols are shown in Fig. 3.3.3c. With the same forcing, AMOC is weaker with hybrid vertical coordinate and with an apparent stronger sensitivity to the forcing protocol.

Figure 3.3.3: Global zonal mean potential temperature difference compared to observations (World Ocean Atlas 2013) for the last 10 years of OMIP1 simulations with isopycnic (a) and hybrid (b) coordinates. AMOC strength of the first cycle of OMIP1 and OMIP2 simulations with isopycnic and hybrid coordinate BLOM (c).

Also extensive testing with fully coupled simulations have been carried out using the hybrid vertical coordinate in BLOM. As for the OMIP simulations, the fully coupled simulations with the hybrid coordinate gives a more realistically stratified Southern Ocean. A cold bias in the subpolar Atlantic seems

more persistent than in the CMIP6 version of NorESM, causing unrealistically large sea ice extent in the Labrador Sea. Further, the Indo-Pacific Warm Pool has persistently been too cold in all tests with the hybrid vertical coordinate causing worsened tropical Pacific climatology compared to the CMIP6 version of NorESM. For these reasons, further development and/or tuning is needed before we can recommend the general use the hybrid vertical coordinate in fully coupled NorESM simulations.

Task 3.2: Parameterization of eddy transport and stirring in the Arctic ocean

a) Inclusion of the effect of topographic PV gradients in eddy parameterizations:

Topographic slopes form potential vorticity gradients which constrain large-scale and mesoscale flows as these cannot cross the gradients without external forcing. Therefore, eddy stirring/mixing across topographic slopes is smaller than across flat-bottom regions. In KeyCLIM we carried out idealized eddy-resolving simulations from which we extracted eddy buoyancy fluxes and calculated diffusivities over sloping bottom topography. Our results suggested that by including an additional length scale, the topographic Rhines scale, we could recover the diagnosed diffusivity as a product of a velocity scale and this length scale. We then restructured the existing eddy parameterization in the target model BLOM to i) be vertically averaged and ii) utilize the new topographic length scale. In addition, we scaled the diffusivity by meanflow and eddy velocity dependent eddy efficiency factor, and this turned out to be important for reducing biases at global scale. We tested the parameterization in an idealized coarse-resolution channel setup, before moving to the global ocean simulations (see more in 3.2 c). The idealized channel model results showed that the new parameterization worked as expected over the slopes in reducing the eddy diffusivity and transport, and were essential in capturing a surface jet that formed in the northern ('prograde') side of the channel. However, despite the success in reproducing the eddy diffusivity structure over the slopes, the mean jets in the model remained too weak and also, in cases, positioned slightly incorrectly. We attributed this remaining bias to the lack of lateral eddy momentum fluxes in our parameterization, a well-known limitation of all coarse-grained ocean models.

b) Inclusion of the effect of sea ice drag in eddy parameterizations:

Not attempted, but a framework is established: the eddy parameterization is constructed such that the overall diffusivity magnitude is calculated as a depth-averaged quantity, with the idea that the vertical structure can be added later. Such a vertical structure function remains an active research topic and would be where the impact of sea ice could enter the eddy parameterizations - essentially reducing eddy mixing just below the sea ice as seen in eddy-resolving simulations.

c) Assessment of the subgrid effects of topography and sea ice on hydrography and circulation in the key region in OMIP sensitivity experiments and in WP6 coupled simulations:

The new topography aware parameterization has been included in the model code and tested in OMIP simulations and was also included in the WP6 coupled simulations. The inclusion of the topographic Rhines scale and eddy efficiency enhances the boundary current strength both in the Arctic (Fig. 3.3.4 orange contours, panels to the left) and in the Antarctic, and acts to warm the Atlantic water layer in the Arctic that has previously suffered from a cold bias in NorESM. At global level the new parameterization acts to warm the Antarctic Bottom Water, and the watermasses below the global thermocline. Whereas the ABW warming reduces the bias, the warming water around thermocline increases the warm bias especially in the Subpolar North Atlantic (Fig. 3.3.4, solid contours on red around 60N).

Task 3.3: Stabilization of the dynamical coupling in the sea ice-ocean system

This task is investigating a resonance, or inconsistency in the dynamical coupling between CICE and BLOM. Similar resonances are also experienced in coupling towards other ocean models, and with other sea ice models. Practical experiments indicate that the resonance can be avoided when the sea ice model is using the same time step as the ocean model, and when they exchange information every time step. However, this is very often an unnecessary short (and computational demanding) time step for the ice model. Also, in the fully coupled NorESM, the thermodynamic coupling of the sea ice model is synchronized with the time step of the atmosphere model. Herefore, in several configurations it will be necessary to use a longer coupling time-step than dictated by the stability of the ocean model.

We have not managed to find a better and more robust solution to this challenge than using the same time step in both models. By looking at the linearized shallow water equations for the ocean, coupled to an ice layer with an ice concentration and thickness, we are able to find exact analytical solutions to some free drift problems (without internal ice stresses). Of particular interest is a solution where the ice cover and ocean are equal and they both respond to the varying surface elevation (wave propagation).

Figure 3.3.4: Temperature anomalies from a control case with diffusivity defined as a product of the local Eady growth rate and squared deformation radius. Top row shows the anomaly when minimum of the topographic Rhines scale and deformation radius is used as the length scale. The bottom row shows the case where the resulting diffusivity is also scaled with anisotropy due to the mean flow. Panels to the left show the mean anomaly at 250-500 m depth in the Arctic and panels to the right show the global zonal mean anomaly. On the left, we also plot 0 m and 2000 m depth contours (black) and relative velocity anomalies (orange; 25%, 50%, 75% contours shown). On the right, we plot the control case bias to the observations (contour levels are -2, -1, 0, 1, and 2, with the 0-contour shown with a thicker line, negative contours are dashed) - whenever dashed (solid) contours are over positive (negative) anomalies, the addition of topographic Rhines scale and scaling by anisotropy act to reduce the mean bias.

This reference solution has been used to study the discrete version of the problem. It is found that the exact behavior is obtained in the discrete model by using an explicit implementation of the ice-ocean stress, which unfortunately is shown to be unstable for very thin ice, and therefore not practical in a more complete situation with wind forcing. The implicit implementation of the stress is stable, but less accurate. However, this simple model also shows the importance of the consistency of the timing of the ocean surface elevation and ocean surface currents which are used in the sea ice model.

3.4 Deliverables

- D3.1 Availability of a jointly tuned code base including atmosphere and ocean PBL developments of WP3 and mixed-phase cloud developments of WP4. As the coupled SCM framework work was abandoned, the originally planned D3.1 was replaced. As explained under task 3.1 e), a physically meaningful tuning of the combined WP3 PBL developments depends on a joint effort with the mixed-phase cloud developments and tuning of WP4. A code base was developed and represents deliverable D3.1.
- D3.2 Documentation of eddy parameterization impacts on OMIP simulations of key region. The documentation is now done through a manuscript that is currently in review (DOI:10.22541/essoar.168394750.04852652/v1). The implementation of the new eddy parameterization is contained in the merged BLOM pull request <https://github.com/NorESMhub/BLOM/pull/253>. As mentioned in section 3.2, the new parameterization does not include the impacts of sea ice drag. We realized that these impacts require more research time than was available in the project, and also some model development as the idealized model setup used for the parameterization development does not include a sea ice component.

- D3.3 Documentation of progress on stabilising sea ice-ocean dynamical coupling. Because of the lack of a clear path forward to improve the situation for the coupled ice-ocean components in NorESM, a short report summarizing the findings from numerical experiments and the analytical analysis is prepared.

WP4 Feedbacks involving clouds and the cryosphere

WP leaders: Trude Storelvmo (UiO), Jens Debernard (MET Norway)

Contributing persons: Petra Langebroek (NORCE), Andreas Born (UiB), Heiko Goelzer (NORCE), Stefan Hofer (UiO)

4.1 Main objectives and goals

Overarching goal: Understand how feedbacks involving the coupled atmosphere, cryosphere and hydrosphere contribute to the accelerated rate of Arctic warming. Secondary goals: (1) Ensure that NorESM reproduces Arctic cloud phase observations; (2) Achieve a realistic NorESM treatment of snow hydrology over sea ice; (3) Perform the first NorESM simulation with interactive land ice to study the mass balance of the Greenland ice sheet.

4.2 Summary and scientific highlights

Research in WP4 can be subdivided into processes and feedbacks related to Arctic sea ice, clouds and land ice, respectively:

- Properties of the snow cover over sea ice are crucial for behaviour of Arctic sea ice in NorESM. We have investigated implications of reduced snow heat conductivity on the sea ice, and also evaluated the melt pond evolution over Arctic sea ice. The melt ponds are interactive in the model and have a strong feedback response to the melting of sea ice.
- For Arctic clouds, it was established early in the project that NorESM simulated cloud phase in accordance with satellite observations (CALIOP retrievals) in the Arctic. However, it was also revealed that this agreement was for the wrong reason, as a bug related to ice formation in NorESM was discovered. Correcting this coding error resulted in a deterioration of the agreement with satellite observations, which was subsequently addressed through adjustments to other processes affecting cloud phase. NorESM was thereafter used to investigate the link between cloud phase and feedbacks in several studies/publications, both in general and in the Arctic specifically.

4.3 Major results

Task 4.1: Realistic treatment of snow hydrology over sea ice

The KeyClim reference version of NorESM (based on the NorESM2-MM CMIP6 configuration) is known to have too much sea ice in the Northern Hemisphere. The ice is both too extensive and too thick. This is in contrast to the low resolution version of the model (NorESM2-LM) which is warmer, but with much more realistic sea ice. The excessive ice in the reference version is attributed to too little downward shortwave radiation during summer, and too little downward longwave radiation during winter, which gives too little summer melt of ice, but also too large winter growth.

The winter growth of sea ice is mainly determined by the heat conductive flux through the ice cover compared with the specific atmospheric and oceanic forcing. A smaller/larger heat conductivity is balanced by and reduced/increased vertical growth of sea ice. As the conductivity of the Arctic snow pack is very variable and highly uncertain, we constructed an experiment (the Snow experiment in WP6) where the snow conductivity is reduced in the ice model compared with the reference, and in addition, a minor reduction in snow albedo was applied. The conductivity was selected by applying a simple equilibrium heat conduction argument with a goal of reducing the resulting sea ice thickness by a factor 2. This gave a conductivity lower than used in the reference run, but within observational constraints for a typical Arctic sea ice snow pack. With this new configuration, the Snow version gives a sea ice area and volume much more in line with observational estimates as shown in Fig. 4.3.1.

Figure 4.3.1: Northern Hemisphere sea ice area (left) and volume (right) for the KeyClim experiments together with observational based estimates (black lines and stars). 10-year running means are shown for all experiments, while the yearly values are kept for the short observational records.

One of the main effects of snow melt water on sea ice is the development of melt ponds, which due to their low albedo, are very important for the surface energy balance of Arctic sea ice. In NorESM the melt ponds are prognostically calculated and there is a positive feedback between increased heating, increased melt pond fraction, and increased sea ice melt.

By using observations from MODIS and MERIS, we have compared melt ponds in satellite products and in the NorESM2-LM historical CMIP6 simulations. Fig. 4.3.2 shows relative monthly mean melt pond coverage (left), and total area of melt ponds (right) for NorESM2-LM and the MODIS and MERIS datasets. From this, it is clear that NorESM has a delayed formation of melt ponds and too few ponds during the peak insulation period in May and June. During July and August, the coverage is more

Figure 4.3.2: Left column: Northern Hemisphere area of melt ponds in NorESM2-LM (upper row), MODIS (middle), and MERIS (lower) for May - September (left to right).

Fig. 4.3.3 shows the seasonal cycle of relative melt pond fraction (melt pond area / sea ice area) for the KeyClim sensitivity experiments together with the reference simulation and the NorESM2-LM simulation. All simulation show similar historical seasonal cycle. Interestingly, the Cloud experiment (Task 4.3) show the highest spring and early summer melt pond fraction most in line with observations. This is also the warmest of the KeyClim simulations. Except Cloud, all other KeyClim experiments have less melt ponds than the LM-version. This supports our conclusion that the delayed melt pond formation in NorESM is mainly a consequence of biased atmospheric forcing.

The analyses of melt pond fraction in NorESM2-LM and observations are prepared as a manuscript which will be submitted to *The Cryosphere*, and this will then fulfill deliverable 4.1. Due to an unclear definition of the melt pond fraction in the MERIS data, we have contacted the developer of these data to clarify the situation. This process have taken almost 5 months this summer, and the consequence was that all figures should be reprocessed with new updated data. The deliverable is therefore further delayed.

Figure 4.3.3: Northern Hemisphere relative melt pond fraction in the KeyClim experiments (colored) and the reference (black) and NorESM2-LM (gray) for the historic reference (left), and a warmer state (right).

Task 4.2: Interactive land ice modelling and impact of local feedbacks

We have completed a series of experiments with NorESM2 including a dynamic Greenland ice sheet model. The runs are performed for two different resolutions of the climate model (LM, MM) and cover the pre-industrial, the historical period and projections to year 2100 under SSP585 forcing. For the high-resolution model version, we have prolonged the projection further to year 2300 following the ScenarioMIP extension for SSP585. Analysis of the experiments and comparison with standard CMIP6 NorESM2 with fixed ice sheet indicates that including the interactive ice sheet model has only a minor impact on global climate (see D6.2). Conversely, we see regional differences over and around Greenland already over the historical period, with increased precipitation over the southern margins in the coupled experiment. In the projection out to year 2300, the coupled ice sheet loses 20% of its volume, predominantly at the margins, leading to increased surface air temperatures as part of the surface mass balance–height feedback. Ice sheet retreat exposes underlying bedrock and tundra with lower albedo which further amplifies marginal warming. Anomalous freshwater fluxes from the melting ice sheet leads to a stratification and cooling of the surface ocean around Greenland in the coupled experiment. This and further analysis is forthcoming in two publications in progress that 1) describe the coupled climate-ice sheet model and 2) evaluates the coupled response in the future projection.

Task 4.3: Determine why and how cloud phase controls Arctic amplification.

An extensive evaluation of NorESMs cloud phase representation in the Arctic has been completed and published by Shaw et al. 2022. Work in Task 4.3 has also led to a new model assessment of the climate impact of black carbon aerosols acting as ice nucleating particles (INPs), building on the implementation of a new laboratory-based ice nucleation parameterizations in CESM2/NorESM2 in McGraw et al. 2020. This produced an effective radiative forcing ranging from -0.30 to 0.02 Wm^{-2} . Finally, three fully coupled simulations have been conducted with modifications to the processes that govern cloud phase, in order to achieve mixed-phase cloud properties consistent with satellite observations. These modifications included scaling of the Wegener-Bergeron-Findeisen process, scaling of the efficiency of heterogeneous ice nucleation, and changes to the temperature-dependent fraction of detrained liquid to total detrained condensate from deep convection. Adjustments were made (A) globally, (B) in the Northern Hemisphere (NH) extratropics, and (C) in the Southern Hemisphere (SH) extratropics, and agreement with observations was sought for both cloud tops and cloud interiors/bulk (see Fig. 4.3.4). The results reveal a hemispheric asymmetry in the way the climate system reacts to changes in cloud phase, and therefore in cloud-climate feedbacks induced by warming outside of the tropics. Specifically, we find that the Northern high latitude warming is strongly amplified when cloud phase in this region is adjusted to observations. However, we also find that cloud phase adjustments outside of this region strongly influence NH extratropical warming, and intriguingly, cloud phase adjustments in the southern hemisphere (SH) high latitudes are almost as influential for NH extratropical warming as those in the region itself Hofer et al. 2023 .

While we were in the process of conducting the above research, a bug in the CESM2/NorESM2 source

Figure 4.3.4: Left column: super-cooled liquid fraction (SLF, in %) vs. temperature for the original (CMIP6 version) of NorESM2, for cloud top (orange) and cloud bulk (blue), and the same quantity for the observationally constrained version of NorESM2. Black curves show SLF from satellite observations (CALIOP), dot-dashed lines represents cloud top and dotted lines cloud bulk. SLF is constrained globally (A), only in the NH extratropics (B) and only in the SH extratropics (C), as indicated by the red frame on the maps in the right column. These maps show that impact on constraining SLF on the net top-of-atmosphere radiation balance (in Wm^{-2}).

code was discovered that led all ice nucleation between -40 and 0 °C to be set to zero. This bug was first brought up in Shaw et al. 2022, and investigated further in Zhu et al. 2022, who found that the bug and the manner in which it was addressed had major implications for the simulated climate feedbacks and climate sensitivity. We have been collaborating closely with NCAR scientists to fix this bug, and together with WP3 tested multiple alternative bugfixes in NorESM2. This resulted in two publications that investigated the influence on ice nucleation on climate feedbacks and climate sensitivity in greater depth Gettelman et al., 2023; McGraw et al., 2023. We finally settled on a bugfix, and have combined this with the observation-based cloud phase adjustments described above, to arrive at the cloud experiments described in WP6.

Task 4.4 Reassessment of role of cloud and cryospheric feedbacks in Arctic amplification

WP4 has provided source code modifications for the purpose of the coupled NorESM2 experiments presented under WP6 (specifically the experiments with extensions "cloud", "cloud2", "iceSheet3" and "snow") and is contributing to the ongoing analyses and publication of the results.

Figure 4.3.5: Sensitivity for a given top-of-the-atmosphere radiative imbalance between 2015-2100 under SSP5-8.5 forcing. A) shows the global cumulative residual top of the atmosphere radiative flux (RESTOM Wm^{-2}) versus the global change in temperature during the SSP5-8.5 period of 2015-2100. The further to the top left the more sensitive is a given simulation. "Control" (red) is the unchanged NorESM2 Control SSP5-8.5 simulation, "S-ET" (southern extratropics, green) refers to the simulation with constrained mixed-phase SLF south of $30^{\circ}S$, "N-ET" (northern extratropics, orange) refers to the simulation with constrained SLF north of $30^{\circ}N$ and "Global" (blue) refers to the simulations where SLF is constrained globally. B) same as A but showing the northern extratropics temperature changes versus the global RESTOM. C) same as A) but showing the southern extratropics temperature changes versus the global RESTOM. Note the different ranges on the y-axis in A, B and C.

4.4 Deliverables

- D4.1 Report on the seasonal cycle of melt ponds in NorESM. Manuscript under preparation for submission to *The Cryosphere*.
- D4.2 Publ. on the impact of a dynamic ice sheet on other components in NorESM2 (covered by a joint publication together with D2.7 and D7.2), (Goelzer et al., Interactive coupling of a Greenland ice sheet model in NorESM2, in prep., intended for submission to GMD)
- D4.3 Publ. on the link between cloud phase and Arctic amplification (completed Shaw et al., 2022; Hofer et al., 2023)
- D4.4 Publ. on the importance of local cloud and cryospheric feedbacks, and their interplay with atmospheric/oceanic dynamical changes, for Arctic amplification (jointly with WP6) (see D6.4)

WP5 Biogeochemical processes and their gas and aerosol

WP leaders: Dirk Olivié (MET Norway), Kirstin Krüger (UiO)

Contributing persons: Dirk Olivié (MET), Kirstin Krüger (UiO), Jörg Schwinger (NORCE), Jerry Tjiputra (NORCE), Dennis Booge (GEOMAR), Birgit Quack (GEOMAR).

5.1 Main objectives and goals

Natural, biogenic emissions can have an impact on the radiative balance of the atmosphere (e.g., bromoform, DMS, isoprene, monoterpene, methane). In a changing climate, the natural emission strengths might be modified due to changes of the concentrations or fluxes, and induce a climate feedback (amplifying or reducing the original climate change). Such a change in emission strength might happen due to changing meteorological conditions like temperature, precipitation, and wind speed, but, for specific species, also due to climate change-induced changes in the ocean due to a warmer and more acidic ocean. Particularly in the Arctic region, changing sea-ice conditions (e.g., retreating sea-ice edge, or ice-free

summer) will very likely have a considerable impact on natural biogenic emissions. An aim of this KeyCLIM Work Package 5 is to extend natural biogenic emissions in the ocean and atmospheric chemistry, allowing to identify and quantify possible climate feedbacks in the Arctic.

5.2 Summary and scientific highlights

Bromoform has been implemented into iHAMMOC, the biogeochemical model component of the ocean in NorESM, and coupled to the atmosphere. As bromoform has the potential to lead to stratospheric ozone loss, estimating its emission strength and evaluating how that might change in a changing climate is relevant. With this model version, simulations of the preindustrial period, the historical period, and a future scenario (SSP5-8.5) have been performed. We have also contributed to the evaluation of DMS ocean emissions in CMIP6 models. DMS is a natural precursor of sulfate aerosol, and is mainly emitted from the ocean. Analysis shows that the models disagree on the future trend of the global DMS, with half of the models showing an increase and the other half a decrease. As part of this work package, tropospheric and stratospheric chemistry have been implemented in NorESM2. This makes the model considerably slower, as it now contains 210 aerosol or gas-phase species compared to 29 in the standard version NorESM2, but allows us to study more processes which might be relevant for climate change. Also with this model version, simulations of the preindustrial period, the historical period, and a future scenario (SSP5-8.5) have been performed. In general, we obtain a model state which is very similar to the climatology of NorESM2.

5.3 Major results

Task 5.1: Improve climate driven and interactive emissions from ocean and land

Evaluation of DMS in CMIP6 models One of the main sources of uncertainties in climate projections is natural aerosols whose relative abundance compared to that of anthropogenic aerosols directly influences the level of the anthropogenic aerosol forcing. Marine dimethylsulfide (DMS) is considered the largest natural source of sulfur to the atmosphere. In WP5, a multi-model study assessing the performance of DMS simulations in CMIP6 models was performed Bock et al., 2021. The study found that CMIP6 models better reproduce the observed DMS in mid to high latitudes, as well as in polar and westerlies marine biomes. The resulting multi-model estimate of contemporary global ocean DMS emissions is 16–24 Tg[S] yr⁻¹, which is narrower than the observational-derived range of 16 to 28 Tg[S] yr⁻¹. The models disagree on the future trend of the global DMS, with half of the models showing an increase and the other half a decrease. At the global scale, these trends are dominated by changes in surface DMS concentrations in all models, irrespective of the air–sea flux parameterisation used. In general, changes in DMS concentrations are correlated with changes in marine productivity; however, marine productivity is poorly constrained in the current generation of ESMs, thus limiting the predictive ability of this relationship. A consensus is found among all models over polar latitudes where an increasing trend is predominantly driven by the retreating sea-ice extent.

Implementation of bromoform in NorESM To test the impact of halogenated very short-lived substances on the atmospheric ozone concentration, and consequently climate projections, a bromoform tracer (CHBr₃) has been implemented in the CMIP6 version of NorESM2. In the ocean biogeochemistry model iHAMOCC, bromoform is produced biologically through phytoplankton processes and removed through photolysis, outgassing to the atmosphere, and decay processes. Once released to the atmosphere, it is freely advected by the atmospheric circulation, and removed by photolysis and reaction with OH.

Bromoform results from a historical model run (1850–2014) will be submitted for publication by the end of the year 2023. This run includes the bromoform production in the biogeochemical ocean module iHAMOCC and its emission to the atmosphere in NorESM (Booge, Tjiputra, Olivié, Quack, Krüger, in preparation). A spin-up run from CMIP6 prior to the historical run was used to equilibrate bromoform concentrations in the model. Model results show that bromoform is mainly outgassing from the ocean to the atmosphere. Global annual mean emissions are 268 pmol m⁻² hr⁻¹ (DJF: 294 pmol m⁻² hr⁻¹, JJA: 253 pmol m⁻² hr⁻¹) with highest annual mean emissions in the upwelling region off the coast of Peru. Lowest annual mean emissions of -1 pmol m⁻² hr⁻¹ are modeled under ice free conditions in the Gulf of Boothia north of Canada (white regions in Fig. 5.3.1). Here, bromoform fluxes are redirected (from the atmosphere to the ocean) due to very low oceanic bromoform concentrations and considerably higher

Figure 5.3.1: Annual (top), DJF (left) and JJA (right) mean oceanic bromoform emissions.

atmospheric mixing ratios, suggesting these oceanic regions act as a sink of atmospheric bromoform. Negative emissions are most likely to occur during winter time in the respective high latitudes (white areas, Fig. 5.3.1). However, bromoform fluxes into the ocean are less pronounced than suggested by other model studies (e.g., Stemmler et al. 2015). These studies used prescribed atmospheric values and did not use a fully coupled ocean-atmosphere model.

The model results are validated with observational data and reveal that resulting oceanic bromoform surface concentrations ($6.61 \pm 3.43 \text{ pmol L}^{-1}$) are well within the range of observational data from the HalOcAt database ($5.02 \pm 4.50 \text{ pmol L}^{-1}$) (Ziska et al. 2013; Fig. 5.3.2a). However, the resulting modeled atmospheric ratios of bromoform ($0.76 \pm 0.39 \text{ ppt}$) are significantly lower than observations ($1.45 \pm 1.11 \text{ pmol L}^{-1}$) (Fig 5.3.2b). A recent estimate by Jia et al. 2023 shows that anthropogenic bromoform contributes to the bromoform emissions by more than 30 % globally and 70 % in the northern hemisphere. However, anthropogenic sources as well as other than biological production by phytoplankton are not part of this model estimate, but lead to higher coastal emissions, which could cause the open ocean mismatch of atmospheric bromoform between model and observations. Additionally, these results question if the general and common use of current flux parameterizations might underestimate bromoform fluxes from the ocean to the atmosphere in different wind regimes as for CO_2 Yang et al., 2022.

Arctic bromoform in a future climate is projected to increase until 2100 compared to current days (Fig. 5.3.3). Our results indicate a strongest absolute difference of annual mean oceanic bromoform concentrations in the high arctic when comparing a 30 year period 1985-2014 from the historical run with the period 2071–2100 from the SSP585 model run. Bromoform emissions will also increase significantly with the strongest change of emissions in coastal areas and future sea ice-free areas. Resulting atmospheric mixing ratios are subsequently also projected to increase over the arctic. Higher sea surface temperatures and less sea ice in a future climate will increase the primary production in the arctic which leads to the increase in bromoform ocean concentrations, emissions, and atmospheric mixing ratios until 2100.

Task 5.2: Extend and improve representation of atmospheric aerosols and chemistry in NorESM

Motivation for full atmospheric chemistry in NorESM The aim of this work was to implement a fully-interactive tropospheric and stratospheric chemistry description in NorESM. We have realized this by coupling the NorESM aerosol scheme with a gas-phase chemistry scheme available in CESM, and a stable full-chemistry version of NorESM exists now. It has been used to perform simulations under various forcing conditions (preindustrial, historical and SSP5-8.5) and we find good agreement between

Figure 5.3.2: Boxplot comparison of NorESM2 model results with HalOcAt observations for oceanic (a) and atmospheric bromoform (b). The line inside the box represents the median, the boxes show the first to third quartile, and the whiskers illustrate the highest and lowest values that are not outliers. The plus signs represent outliers.

Figure 5.3.3: Annual mean averages of oceanic bromoform (upper panel), bromoform emissions (middle panel) and atmospheric bromoform (lower panel) over the time period of 1985–2014 (left column), 2071–2100 (middle column) and the differences between the historical and future run time periods (right column). Red solid and dashed lines in the left and middle column indicate a minimum of 90% and 50% of annual mean sea ice fraction, respectively.

NorESM and CESM, which will be illustrated further in this section.

A full-chemistry version of NorESM is a significant step forward and it should lead to :

- an improved description of aerosols in NorESM, as the oxidants playing a role in the formation of secondary aerosol, are now interactively calculated (instead of being prescribed climatologies);
- a widening of the scope of emission reduction impact studies. Within the group of short-lived climate forcers, we could with NorESM up to now only quantify the role of SO₂, OC and BC emission reductions on climate (via aerosol). With the new setup we can also look at the impact of emission reductions in NO_x, CO and VOCs emissions (via ozone and methane);
- lower dependence on external datasets. The new model is less dependent on external boundary conditions, such as climatologies for ozone and oxidants, which were traditionally provided by NCAR based on simulations with CESM2-WACCM;
- a more complete Earth-System approach for NorESM. The effect of a changing climate on the strength of natural emissions (e.g., NO_x from lightning, BVOC from vegetation, NO_x and CO from soil, CH₄ from permafrost thawing, bromoform from the ocean) will now be possible to be studied. Having a full-chemistry allows us to take into account the effect of these changing emissions on climate; and
- a better representation of the air-quality, as we now both model aerosols and ozone explicitly and interactively.

Description of the full-chemistry implementation in NorESM The original version of NorESM Seland et al., 2020 contains a detailed representation of atmospheric aerosol described by 21 tracers, but a limited description of gas-phase chemistry (8 tracers, and 4 climatologies). We have now coupled this aerosol scheme with an existing chemistry scheme from CESM, i.e., the so-called TS1 scheme Emmons et al., 2020. The TS1 scheme has tropospheric and stratospheric chemistry with a total of 221 tracers, and includes the MAM4 aerosol scheme. The coupling of the TS1 scheme with the aerosols of NorESM results in a scheme with a total of 210 tracers. As a consequence, the number of emitted species is now considerably higher than in the standard NorESM version, and preparation of extra emissions files for biomass burning and anthropogenic emissions was required. Ozone is now calculated on-line by the chemistry, and its concentration is used in the radiation code (instead of the prescribed ozone climatology in NorESM).

Also the treatment of long-lived green-house gases (GHGs) has changed. In standard NorESM, GHG (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, CFC-11 and CFC-12) concentrations are prescribed at the surface (with a possible temporal evolution), and simple predefined profiles are used to obtain the vertical distribution, used in the radiative transfer calculation. In the new version, these GHGs are now part of the chemistry scheme, and described as 3-dimensional distributions where the vertical profile is now determined by transport and chemical loss. To avoid large biases in the concentration (as the sources of these GHGs are not very accurately known), we still prescribe the GHG concentrations at the surface. In addition to GHGs, also surface concentration of ozone depleting substances (ODSs) are nudged towards observed values, where we have followed the CESM setup.

The only ODS we treat differently in NorESM compared to CESM is bromoform (CHBr₃). In CESM, a CHBr₃ concentration of 1 ppt is prescribed in the lowest atmospheric layer (constant over the globe and over time), whereas in the full chemistry version of NorESM we use now CHBr₃ emissions, based on an interactive coupling with the biogeochemistry in the ocean (see Task 5.1). Compared to the NorESM2 version described above, the reaction of CHBr₃ with OH is calculated using on-line OH concentrations instead of an OH climatology, and the fate of the decay products is now further followed (with possible impact on stratospheric ozone).

The heterogeneous chemical reactions take into account the surface area from the NorESM aerosols, both in the troposphere and the stratosphere (e.g., relevant to correctly model the stratospheric ozone concentration). Up to now we did not explicitly model stratospheric sulfate aerosol, and the impact of large explosive volcanoes (leading in reality to sulfate aerosols in the stratosphere) was only taken into account by using a prescribed (external) climatology of stratospheric aerosol optical depth (AOD). In the new version, we now have explicit formation of stratospheric aerosol from carbonyl sulfide (OCS) and SO₂. OCS is now an explicit chemical species (nudged at the surface to prescribed concentrations), and explicit SO₂ emissions from explosive volcanic eruptions are now injected in the stratosphere. To obtain realistic stratospheric AODs (both after larger volcanic eruptions as well as during more quiet

periods), we noticed that we had to emit part of the SO₂ (10 %) directly as sulphate (SO₄) : this ratio is higher than what we use for tropospheric emissions (only 2.5 % is emitted as SO₄), and is also different from the ratio in CESM which emits all its volcanic sulfur as SO₂ (0 % as SO₄).

In addition to the modifications described above needed for the implementation of tropospheric and stratospheric chemistry, we have performed three additional small updates to the model:

- the monoterpene emissions (leading to secondary organic aerosol (SOA)) have been slightly increased : similar to CESM we take into account more species coming from the land (MEGAN2.1) which are lumped into the atmospheric monoterpene tracer;
- the dry deposition of aerosols has been slightly modified. This change mainly causes an increase in the lifetime of large dust and sea-salt particles; and
- reaction rates for the oxidation of monoterpene and isoprene have been updated to the values used in CESM.

Finally, although we have introduced stratospheric chemistry, the top of the model has not been increased and remains relatively low. Also the number of levels has remained unchanged on 32.

Results In this section we describe some results obtained with the full-chemistry version of NorESM, and compare them with results from the standard version of NorESM and full-chemistry version of CESM. We show results from the following simulations :

- CESM simulations with TS1 full-chemistry (CESM2-chem) on 2°x2° and 1°x1° horizontal resolution over the historical period (the 1°x1° simulations is limited to 1970–2014 period);
- standard NorESM (NorESM2) simulations on 1°x1° horizontal resolution under pre-industrial condition and for the historical period; and
- full-chemistry NorESM (NorESM2-chem) simulation on 1°x1° horizontal resolution under pre-industrial condition, for the historical period and for the SSP5-8.5 scenario (only shown until 2050).

Figure 5.3.4 (left) shows the evolution of the TOA radiation flux under pre-industrial conditions in NorESM2 and NorESM2-chem. Any imbalance over a longer time will induce a cooling or warming of the global-mean ocean temperatures. The full-chemistry version shows a slightly stronger cooling (-0.05 W m^{-2}) than standard NorESM (-0.01 W m^{-2}), based on the (first) 160 years. However, as the drift is still reasonably small even in the full-chemistry simulation, we have opted for no additional tuning of NorESM2-chem. We attribute this additional cooling to the higher aerosol load (mainly sea-salt), but also other modifications might contribute. The global mean surface (2 m) temperature evolution over the historical period is very similar to the evolution in the standard model setup, although in general the temperature is around 0.1 K lower.

Figure 5.3.5 shows total (all aerosol species together) aerosol optical depth (visual wavelength) and the sea-salt aerosol optical depth (at 550 nm). Peaks in global AOD are clearly visible in the aftermath of strong volcanic eruptions. The AOD in NorESM has increased by around 0.02 when going from the standard to the full-chemistry version, mainly caused by an increase in sea-salt (AOD). The AOD signal from volcanic eruptions is similar for both NorESM versions. CESM2 at 2°x2° resolution has considerably higher AOD, mainly because it has much stronger dust emissions (and therefore dust AOD) due to a different emissions scaling factor.

Figure 5.3.6 (left) shows modeled global- and annual-mean total ozone column. The total ozone column in NorESM2-chem is now slightly higher than in standard NorESM2, around 5 Dobson units (DU). The right panel of Fig. 5.3.6 shows the total ozone column averaged over the land areas of 90°S–28°S for the SON season. We find reasonable agreement between the climatology used in NorESM2, and the interactively calculate ozone columns of NorESM2-chem and CESM2-chem. Figure 5.3.6 (bottom) shows atmospheric ozone mixing ratios at the surface. Ozone surface concentrations are very similar between NorESM2-chem and the climatology used in standard NorESM2. CESM2-chem on 2°x2° horizontal resolution shows slightly lower surface ozone values, probably due to smaller NO_x emissions from lightning.

The amount of ozone depletion taking place in spring over Antarctica, is strongly determined by the chlorine and bromine loading in the (polar) stratosphere. Figure 5.3.7 shows the total inorganic chlorine (Cly) and bromine (Bry) loading at 51.7 hPa (lower stratosphere). The loading for Cly is very similar

Figure 5.3.4: (left) Global-mean TOA net radiation (positive downward) and (right) global volume-mean ocean temperature under pre-industrial conditions. (bottom) Global-mean surface air (2m) temperature over the historical period and SSP5-8.5 scenario up to 2055 (only for NorESM2-chem).

Figure 5.3.5: Global-mean total AOD in the visible wavelength band (left) and sea-salt AOD at 550 nm (right).

Figure 5.3.6: (left) Global- and annual-mean ozone column burden; (right) Ozone column burden averaged over 90°S-28°S (land only) in Sep-Oct-Nov. (bottom) Global- and annual mean surface ozone mixing ratio.

Figure 5.3.7: Global-mean total inorganic chlorine (Cly, left) and bromine (Bry, right) at 51.7 hPa.

between NorESM2-chem and CESM2-chem. We see, however, a difference for Bry : in NorESM2-chem the mixing ratios are around 1ppt lower than in CESM2-chem. This is probably caused by the difference in the treatment of CHBr₃ (bromoform) in both models. As mentioned above, in CESM2-TS1, CHBr₃ mixing ratios are prescribed at the surface with a fixed values of 1 ppt, whereas in NorESM2-fullchem on-line calculated CHBr₃ emissions are used, resulting from biogeochemical activity in the ocean (see former section on implementation of CHBr₃ in the ocean component of NorESM).

We aim to further evaluate the impact of the introduction of extensive gas-phase chemistry in NorESM. We will focus on how the formation of secondary aerosols and the aging of primary aerosols changes, and on the comparison of NorESM2-chem results with observations.

5.4 Deliverables

- D5.1 Report on HAMOCC implementation of extended trace gas and aerosol interaction (completed). Code can be found at :

<https://github.com/NorESMhub/BLOM/tree/feature-hamocc-vs1s>
<https://github.com/NorESMhub/CAM/tree/feature-hamocc-vs1s>

<https://github.com/NorESMhub/cime/tree/feature-hamocc-vsls>

- D5.2 Publication on validation of interactive model emission estimates. A manuscript on modeling DMS in present and future climate is published Bock et al., 2021. A manuscript on the evaluation of bromoform in a historical simulation (1850-2014) is currently being written up (Booge, D., J.F. Tjiputra, D.J.L. Olivié, B. Quack, and K. Krüger, Natural marine bromoform emissions in the fully coupled ocean-atmosphere-model NorESM2, to be submitted to GMD.)
- D5.3 Publication validation of atmospheric composition based on new emissions, atmospheric chemistry and aerosols. A manuscript describing the full-chemistry version of NorESM2 is in preparation (Olivié et al., Evaluation of atmospheric chemistry in NorESM2, in prep., to be submitted to GMD in 2024.)
- D5.4 Publication impact of ice-free Arctic Ocean on biogeochemical processes, gas and aerosol climate interactions. A manuscript on bromoform in a future summer sea-ice free Arctic is currently in preparation (Booge, D., J.F. Tjiputra, D.J.L. Olivié, B. Quack, and K. Krüger, Future bromoform trend in the Arctic in the fully coupled ocean-atmosphere-model NorESM2, in prep., to be submitted 2024.)

WP6 Assessment of model enhancements through coordinated Earth system experiments

WP leaders: Lise Seland Graff (MET Norway), Jerry Tjiputra (NORCE)

Contributing persons: Dirk Olivié (MET Norway), Øyvind Seland (MET Norway), Jens Debernard (MET Norway), Jörg Schwinger (NORCE), Thomas Toniazzo (NORCE), Mats Bentsen (NORCE), Chungheng Guo (NORCE), Mehmet Iliack (NORCE), Yanchun He (NERSC), Aleks Nummelin (NORCE), Heiko Goelzer (NORCE), Petra Langebroek (NORCE), Andreas Born (UiB), Trude Storelvmo (UiO), Stefan Hofer (UiO), Jonah Shaw (UiO), Zachary McGraw (UiO), Pål Erik Isachsen (UiO), Ada Gjermundsen (MET Norway), Andrea Rosendahl (MET Norway and UiB), and Michael Schulz (MET Norway)

6.1 Main objectives and goals

The objective of WP6 is to assess the model developments from WPs 3-5 in a set of fully coupled sensitivity experiments with NorESM2. Each component development is assessed individually in a set of transient historical and future scenario simulations, following the CMIP6 protocols for the historical experiment and the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway with a 8.5 W m^{-2} increase in radiative forcing (compared to pre-industrial levels) by the end of the 21st Century (Eyring et al., 2016; O'Neill et al., 2016, ssp585). The impact of individual developments is evaluated by (1) comparing the modified historical experiments to the baseline historical experiment from CMIP6, to observations, and to reanalysis data (D6.2) and (2) by comparing the future response in the modified scenario experiments to that in corresponding baseline experiments from CMIP6 (D6.3). The experiments have also been investigated in other WPs.

6.2 Summary and scientific highlights

- We have successfully carried out a comprehensive set of fully coupled historical and future scenario experiments (Table 1) with improved mixed-phase cloud processes (hist-cloud, ssp585-cloud, hist-cloud2, ssp370-cloud2, ssp585-cloud2), with improved eddy processes in the upper ocean (hist-eddy, ssp585-eddy), with an active Greenland land-ice component (hist-iceSheet3, ssp585-iceSheet3), with interactive ozone chemistry (hist-ozone, ssp585-ozone), and with improved representation of snow-on-sea-ice processes (hist-snow, ssp585-snow). We have also completed an experiment set where the aerosols are kept at pre-industrial levels (hist-piAerOxid, ssp370-piAerOxid, ssp585-piAerOxid) and we have examined experiments with a higher-resolution ocean model (hist-HR, ssp585-HR), and a future experiment with a fixed reduction in the Arctic sea ice (fut-fixSIC). The latter two are in-kind from other projects.

Table 1: Overview of the WP6 experiments. The experiment id is given in the first column. A description of the introduced changes is given in the second column. The status of the experiment is given in the third. The status of the production and archiving of CMIP6 compliant output (CMOR-ized) is given in the fourth column. The experiments ("HR" and "fixSIC") are in-kind contributions from other projects. Note that each experiment consists of simulations for both the historical and future climates (SSP5-8.5 and/or SSP3-7.0), with forcing protocols following the relevant CMIP6 protocol.

Experiment	Description	Status	CMOR
hist-cloud, ssp585-cloud	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with improved mixed-phase-cloud processes	Completed	Completed
hist-cloud2, ssp370-cloud2, ssp585-cloud2	Tuned version of cloud experiments + additional scenario (SSP3-7.0)	Completed	Completed
hist-eddy, ssp585-eddy	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with improved eddy processes in the upper ocean	Completed	Completed
hist-iceSheet3, ssp585-iceSheet3	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with the Greenland land-ice component active	Completed	Completed
hist-ozone, ssp585-ozone	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with improved ozone and VLSL	Completed	Completed
hist-snow, ssp585-snow	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with improved snow (on sea ice) processes	Completed	Completed
hist-piAerOxid, ssp370-piAerOxid, ssp585-piAerOxid	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios, but without anthropogenic aerosols	Completed	Completed
hist-HR, ssp585-HR	Historical and SSP5-8.5 scenarios with high-resolution ocean	Completed	Completed
fut-fixSIC	Future experiment with fixed Arctic sea ice	Completed	Completed
hist-pblAtm, ssp585-pblAtm	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with improvements in the atmospheric PBL	Omitted	n/a
hist-pblOcn, ssp585-pblOcn	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with hybrid coordinates in the ocean	Omitted	n/a
hist-all-inclusive, ssp585-all-inclusive	As in the CMIP6 historical and SSP5-8.5 scenario, but with several improvements combined	Omitted	n/a

- The extensive set of model output from all experiments has moreover been post-processed to produce CMIP6-compliant (CMOR-ized) output which has been made available to the consortium (D6.1).
- Finally, we have performed a joint analysis of present-day climate in the historical experiments (D6.2) and the influence of the model improvements on response to future climate change (D6.3; attached to this report).

6.3 Major results

To make sure that the model updates from WPs 3–5 were tested in the fully coupled model in a consistent and comparable way, we initially developed a common protocol including a common set of output variables to facilitate analysis. We also developed an interactive spreadsheet which provides a comprehensive overview of the full set of experiments and the relevant details.

To enable conversion of the raw output from the WP6 experiments to standardized CMIP6 compliant output, we also set up a customized KeyCLIM branch in the post-processing tool `noresm2cmor`. This tool is a FORTRAN and shell-script-based tool built on the Climate Model Output Rewriter (CMOR) libraries and that is tailored for the NorESM. We have applied this tool to the full set of experiments to produce a CMIP6-like output database that has been made available to the whole consortium (D6.1).

6.3.1 Experiments

The cloud experiments. In the first set of experiments with improved mixed-phase clouds (`hist-cloud`, `ssp585-cloud`), the representation of mixed-phase clouds was improved by tuning the Wegener-Bergeron-Findeisen process. Also, a model bug related to the amount of ice-nucleating particles in mixed-phase processes and the temperature at which detrained particles from convective cores go from solid to liquid phase was rectified. Results showed that the resulting super-cooled liquid fraction was closer to the observed (see task 4.3 description and figure 4.3.4 for further details). The model was however also shown to have a negative top-of-the-atmosphere radiative imbalance and hence is too cold throughout the simulated period.

To rectify the radiative imbalance, a improved version of the cloud experiments was carried out in the gamma parameter in the CLUBB scheme was adjusted in order to achieve a balanced model (`hist-cloud2`, `ssp370-cloud2`, `ssp585-cloud2`) with a near-surface temperature that is more similar to that seen for the CMIP6 baseline experiments (see progress report from December 2022 for more details). Results from the cloud2 experiments moreover show that several biases in the model are improved, including temperature and storm-track activity. See task 4.3, D6.2, and D6.3 for further details.

The eddy experiments. In the eddy experiments (`hist-eddy`, `ssp585-eddy`), modifications are introduced into the ways eddies are parameterized in the ocean model, including a 2-D formulation of Gent-McWilliam mixing, the effect of eddy-mean-flow interaction by eddy anisotropy, and the diffusivity reduction due to the topographic Rhines-scale-induced potential-vorticity gradient. These changes generally act to reduce the eddy diffusivities in the tropical and subtropical oceans, and in the Arctic Ocean. In the Southern Ocean and Western Boundary Currents, the effect is the opposite, that is, diffusivity is increased. This results in a weakening of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation compared to the CMIP6 baseline. Also, the near-surface temperature is reduced compared to the baseline, particularly the 1960s and 1990s, and consequently the Arctic sea-ice cover and thickness increases. Task 3.2 and D6.3 for further details.

The ice-sheet experiments. In the ice-sheet experiments (`hist-iceSheet3`, `ssp585-iceSheet3`), the interactive Greenland ice-sheet model CISM was coupled with the other components of NorESM2. This results in a Greenland ice sheet that is able to respond to changes in the surface energy and mass balance provided by the land model and that delivers freshwater and solid ice fluxes to the ocean via the land model. The influence on the global climate is modest, but there are evident local changes over and around Greenland with increased near-surface temperatures due to loss of ice sheet elevation and warming over newly exposed tundra. Freshwater fluxes from the ice sheet into the ocean acts to stratify and cool the surrounding surface ocean. See task 4.2 and D6.3 for further details.

The ozone experiments. In the ozone experiments (hist-ozone, ssp585-ozone), the TS1 chemistry scheme is activated in the model in order to calculate tropospheric and stratospheric chemistry. The default behavior of the model is to prescribe greenhouse gases and ozone from forcing files. Aerosols are prognostically calculated on both cases, but are also coupled to the chemistry in the ozone runs. See task 5.2 and D6.3 for further details.

The snow (on sea ice) experiments. In the snow (on sea ice) experiments (hist-snow, ssp585-snow), the representation of the snow hydrology over sea ice is improved by reducing snow conductivity and snow albedo to achieve better agreement between the modeled and observed Arctic sea-ice volume. Results show that the Arctic sea-ice volume in the hist-snow is more similar to the observed (and to NorESM2-LM, which is shown to have smaller sea-ice errors than NorESM2-MM; see Seland et al., 2020). See task 4.1 and D6.3 for further details.

The aerosol experiments. In the experiments without anthropogenic aerosols (hist-piAerOxid, ssp370-piAerOxid, ssp585-piAerOxid), emissions of aerosols, aerosol pre-cursors and oxidant concentrations are kept at pre-industrial levels. Results showed that this results a larger increase in near-surface temperatures compared to in the CMIP6 baseline experiments (the CMIP6 historical and ssp585). See D6.2 and D6.3 for further details.

The fixed sea ice experiment. In the fixed sea-ice experiments (fut-fixSIC), the future sea-ice concentration in the Arctic were constrained to conditions consistent with a 2 K warming. Results showed that under future warming, most of the local and low-level warming in the Arctic can be associated with the Arctic sea-ice loss. Changes in top-of-the-atmosphere radiative balance and the mid-latitude atmospheric circulation were however very small, in contrast to what is typically seen under future scenarios like ssp585.

The high-resolution ocean experiments. In the experiments with a higher-resolution ocean (hist-HR, ssp585-HR), the NorESM2 was coupled with a quarter-degree version of the ocean model. Results showed that the projected future warming was even stronger with the higher-resolution ocean, however, this was tied to inadequate spin-up time due to the very high computational costs of running the model configuration.

6.3.2 Combined results

A synthesis paper focusing on the impact of the targeted model updates in the WP6 experiments on the future climate response is currently under development and a draft version is attached to this report (D6.3). The paper will be further developed moving forward and submitted to a peer-reviewed journal (most likely Earth System Dynamics). Below, we consider selected key results. For further details and results, please see the attached draft manuscript.

The sensitivity experiments (cloud2, eddy, iceSheet3, snow, ozone, and piAerOxid) all undergo enhanced warming over the Arctic during winter (DJF) compared to the reference (CMIP6) response (Figure 6.3.1). The reference warming is defined as the warming found in the CMIP6 ssp585 experiment with respect to the CMIP6 historical experiments, using the last 30 years in each case (panel a). The additional future warming is defined as the future warming of the sensitivity experiments with the reference response subtracted, and is shown for cloud2 (b), eddy (c), icesheet3 (d), snow (e), ozone (f), and piAeroxid (g). For reference, we also show the warming range for the Tier 1 ScenarioMIP experiments (ssp585–ssp126; h). The additional arctic warming is strongest in cloud2 (3.5 K) and smallest in snow (0.4 K) and ozone (0.1 K) with the changes mostly being insignificant in the latter two cases.

To gain further insights into which processes are causing the warming, we decompose the surface temperature contribution into six feedbacks using the surface energy balance approach of Lu and Cai 2009 and Boeke and Taylor 2018. With this method, the change in surface temperature can be approximated by the sum of the contributions due to the surface albedo feedback (SAF), cloud feedback (CRE), non-SAF shortwave clear-sky feedbacks (SWCS), longwave clear-sky feedback (LWCS), changes in ocean heat storage (HSTORE), and changes in surface fluxes of latent and sensible heat (HFLUX). Results show that the surface temperature changes are dominated by CRE, LWCS, HFLUX, and HSTORE, with the variability of the contributions across the experiments being largest for LWCS (Figure 6.3.2a). Consistent with the warming response (Figure 6.3.1), the sum of the contributions is largest for cloud2 and smallest for ozone (Figure 6.3.2a). The results suggest that further investigations should focus on processes of key

Figure 6.3.1: Future change in Arctic near-surface temperature (colors) during winter (DJF). Panel a shows the future warming for ssp585 (ssp585–historical). Panels b–g show the additional future warming with respect to the baseline warming for cloud2 [(ssp585–cloud2–hist–cloud2)–(ssp585–historical); b], eddy [(ssp585–eddy–hist–eddy)–(ssp585–historical); c], iceSheet3 [(ssp585–iceSheet3–hist–iceSheet3)–(ssp585–historical); d], snow [(ssp585–snow–hist–snow)–(ssp585–historical); e], ozone [(ssp585–ozone–hist–ozone)–(ssp585–historical); f], and piAerOxid [(ssp585–piAerOxid–hist–piAerOxid)–(ssp585–historical); h]. Panel h shows the ScenarioMIP range (ssp585–ssp126). The area average and the root-mean-square-difference (rmsd) is given in the upper right and left titles above each panel. Selected contours from the respective historical climatologies (solid black lines) are shown for reference. We use years 2071–2100 for the scenarios and 1985–2014 for the historical/hist experiments in all cases. White dots indicate non-significant changes according to a two-sided T-test.

importance for the dominant feedbacks such as those associated with clouds (CRE), changes in atmospheric conditions like air temperature, the water-vapor content, and the CO₂ concentrations (LWCS), changes in latent and sensible heat fluxes (HFLUX), and changes in ocean heat storage (HSTORE).

6.4 Deliverables

We have successfully completed the majority of the planned experiments (Table 1). The experiment sets with improvements in the atmospheric planetary boundary layer (hist-pblAtm, ssp585-pblAtm), with the hybrid coordinates in the ocean (hist-pblOcn, ssp585-pblOcn), and with several improvements combined (hist-all-inclusive, ssp585-all-inclusive) however had to be omitted as it was not permissible to complete this work within the time frame of the project. The eligible model updates will however be included in an upcoming release of NorESM, currently scheduled for 2024.

- D6.1 Standardized baseline and sensitivity model outputs in project archive located in the folder /projects/NS9252K/KeyCLIM_CMOR on NIRD and report (completed; available at https://drive.google.com/file/d/1h4byp4vhgDzqi60MN5F9QgSA2e7BWQZR/view?usp=drive_link)
- D6.2 Report of basic diagnostic of ECV performance in NorESM (completed; available at https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jbhsMXKPkpyC13krigonoMxsRsbcKcrE/view?usp=drive_link)
- D6.3 Synthesis publication on the impacts of the targeted process improvements on future climates (manuscript is in progress and will be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal (Earth System

Figure 6.3.2: Overview of future changes in terms of the surface albedo feedback (SAF), cloud feedback (CRE), non-SAF shortwave clear-sky feedbacks (SWCS), longwave clear-sky feedback (LWCS), changes in ocean heat storage (HSTORE), and changes in surface fluxes of latent and sensible heat (HFLUX) as diagnosed by surface energy budget decomposition. Panel a) shows the six feedbacks (SAF, CRE, LWCS, HFLUX, HSTORE, and SWCS) against their additional surface temperature contribution with the different colored bars showing cloud2 (red), eddy (blue), iceSheet3 (green), snow (orange), ozone diff-diff (purple), piAerOxid (brown), and the ScenarioMIP range (ssp585–ssp126; black). Note that all values are with the reference response subtracted.

Dynamics) within a few months; the draft version is attached to this report as an appendix)

WP7 Analysis of irreversible climate change with the enhanced NorESM

WP leaders: Andreas Born (UiB), Michael Schulz (MET)

Contributing persons: Andreas Born (UiB), Chuncheng Guo (NORCE), Mehmet Ilicak (NORCE), Mats Bentsen (NORCE), Aleksi Nummelin (NORCE), Petra Langebroek (NORCE), Heiko Goelzer (NORCE), Ada Gjermundsen (MET), Marte Sofie Buraas (UiO), Michael Schulz (MET), Konstanze Haubner (UiB, from 01.2022)

7.1 Main objectives and goals

Overarching: In-depth analysis of enhanced NorESM simulations focusing on coupled feedbacks leading to potentially irreversible climate change. Secondary: (1) Establish how model enhancements modify the sensitivity to external forcing; (2) Clarify whether previously non-interactive or coarsely resolved components introduce new or shift existing tipping points; (3) Estimate the limits of irreversible climate change with the enhanced NorESM.

7.2 Summary and scientific highlights

Progress in WP7 was mostly as planned. Most simulations have been carried out and analysis is underway. Several publications are either in revision or final preparation. The exception is a simulation of the historical period with the new hybrid ocean coordinate, which could not be carried out as planned due to unforeseen difficulties in the development of the hybrid coordinate.

7.3 Major results

Task 7.1: Impact of high resolution ocean modeling and eddy parameterization on northern latitude climate

This task includes analyzing the effect of 1) increased horizontal resolution and 2) enhanced parameterization of mesoscale eddies on the Arctic Ocean and climate. Analysis of these simulations will continue until M54, and the results will be summarized in a report. Selected results are highlighted below.

Analyzing the effect of increased horizontal resolution

We analyzed the representation of the Arctic Ocean water masses in a high-resolution NorESM setup, i.e. NorESM2-MX, with an oceanic resolution of 1/8-deg and atmospheric resolution of 1-deg. The model was run for 36 years. Such a high-resolution ocean is able to resolve (albeit not fully) mesoscale eddies and the rich structures of ocean currents and fronts, as shown in the top right panel below in Fig. 7.3.1. While still in the spin-up phase without getting into a quasi-equilibrium state, the model shows promising results in improving the basin-averaged distribution of the Atlantic Water (figure not shown), compared to its lower-resolution counterpart (e.g. the CMIP6 standard resolution of 1-deg ocean). However, close scrutiny of the geographical distribution of the Atlantic Water (see top two panels in Fig. 7.3.1) indicates that the model misrepresents the Atlantic Water pathway, i.e. instead of turning eastward above/around the Yermak Plateau after passing the Fram Strait (and then flow cyclonically along the slope), the majority of the water seems to “overshoot” to the north of Greenland and then to the North Pole. This seemingly anticyclonically oriented flow is also shared by CESM-HR (see bottom two panels in Fig. 7.3.1), which has an equally high resolution (0.1-deg in the ocean, 0.25-deg in the atmosphere). While the origins of such biases might be difficult to pinpoint and could be well due to the inadequacies of the ocean model, previous studies (Hinrichs et al., 2021) have also pointed to the atmospheric wind bias as playing a significant role, which is able to reverse the subsurface flow from cyclonic to anticyclonic. Whether this is also the case in NorESM2-MX needs to be further investigated. The current simulation length of NorESM2-MX limits the usefulness for quantifying changes in deep water formation.

Analyzing the effect of enhanced parameterization of mesoscale eddies on the Arctic Ocean and climate.

The coupled PI control and historical simulations with the new bottom slope aware eddy parametrization have been completed (WP3), and analysis of results is underway. Preliminary results show a more extensive Arctic sea ice (compare to the PI control simulation) during the mid-20th century and a global cooling hiatus until the 1980s before a rapid warming through the 1990s. This result deviates from the PI control and historical (3-ensemble members) simulations performed by the CMIP6 version of NorESM and merits further investigation, for example by running more ensemble members and/or by checking if aerosol implementation/representation is correct in the model.

Task 7.2: Coupled climate-ice sheet feedbacks

We have successfully completed a simulation of NorESM2-MM with and without an interactive Greenland ice sheet from 1850 to 2300 under extended ssp-585 forcing, see WP4.2 and WP6 for more technical details.

NorESM2 shows the same overall trends throughout the climate components including spatial differences especially around Greenland with and without the climate-ice sheet feedback. Hence, the coupling routine to include an evolving ice sheet is successfully included into NorESM2 and can be used in the future for various time periods and sensitivity studies.

The overall warming trends in air and ocean temperatures dominate changes in the climate system leading to a mean global surface air temperature increase of 12°C. Yet, surface air temperatures over the Greenland are up to 6°C warmer over the Greenland ice margins than without an evolving ice sheet. This difference is mainly driven by the lapse rate effect: With a thinning ice sheet, the surface air temperatures are computed in lower altitudes and thereby increase. The difference in air temperatures further impact surface ocean temperatures to be 2°C higher around Greenland in the coupled simulation compared to the standard NorESM2 simulation. However, the climate-ice sheet feedback does not show a strong signal in the Atlantic stratification change over time, which, like the sea ice cover, is dominated by the strong warming signal within NorESM2 after 2100. A publication discussing the above observations is in preparation with the aimed submission date in February 2024.

Figure 7.3.1: Top panels: NorESM-MX simulations of (left) a 5-year average and (right) a monthly “snapshot” of temperature at a depth level of 400 m, e.g. the approximate depth of the core Atlantic Water. Bottom panels: the same for CESM-HR (the left panel is 20-year average).

Task 7.3: Quantify changes in ocean carbon chemistry due to an enhanced mixed layer

A new hybrid vertical discretisation scheme was implemented in the NorESM ocean component BLOM/iHAMOCC in 2022, whereby the bulk surface mixed layer formulation (isopycnal scheme) used for CMIP6 simulations was replaced by a sequence of fixed depth coordinates throughout the surface mixed layer. The new scheme has demonstrated capability for better preservation of water mass properties, notably in regions of deep convection, but has been difficult to stabilize for pre-industrial conditions. Hence, a historical model run with the hybrid scheme has not been available for evaluation, and we have therefore not been able to carry out a comparison with observational data sets as originally planned. As a result, we have not been able to complete D7.3 “Publication on carbon chemistry changes with enhanced mixed layer” within the time frame of the KeyCLIM project.

A limited evaluation of the hybrid scheme has been carried out with reference to ocean-only (OMIP-1 and OMIP-2) pre-industrial control runs. This evaluation has been carried out by comparing hybrid scheme model output with reference isopycnal scheme model output. Most of the analyzed tracer time-series (net CO_2 flux, primary and export production, CaCO_3 export) stabilize near the reference values, except DMS which increase by approximately 20% compared to both reference runs. The vertically integrated primary productivity shows a pronounced increase in equatorial regions compensated by a reduction in mid-latitude regions. These tests provide some assurance that the ocean carbon chemistry representation in NorESM remain within reasonable bounds with the new hybrid vertical discretisation scheme, but a historical model run will be required to quantify the changes and provide a more complete assessment of the model performance. The development of the hybrid vertical discretisation scheme is carried forward in a new version of NorESM with updated model components, and work continues with the aim to obtain a stabilized configuration for the pre-industrial condition that will facilitate historical model runs.

As contribution to the task regarding limits of irreversibility, we have examined an extended ZECMIP (“zero emission commitment”) B3 experiment, defined by an initial cumulative CO_2 emission of 2000 PgC following a bell-shaped curve pathway. The original simulation run, consisting of a period of emissions distributed over 100 years followed by 300 years of zero emissions, has been extended by a further 400 years of zero emissions to examine the long term evolution of the climate system. The simulation shows that the net downward CO_2 flux, while steadily decreasing after the initial emission period, remains positive throughout the 800 year simulation and reach an end value of 0.5 Pg/year. While the ocean surface temperature reach a steady state, warming continues in the deep ocean, in particular in the Atlantic ocean. Hence, even after a 700 year period of zero emissions, the after-effects of the initial 2000 PgC emission is clearly present in the climate system. A publication based on the ZECMIP runs

Figure 7.3.2: Surface Air temperature changes (in °C) in (i) absolute values (upper row), (ii) relative changes since present day (PD) (middle row) and (iii) differences between NorESM2 with and without an evolving Greenland ice sheet (bottom row). Results shown represent the mean values over a 30yr climatology from 2015 to 2034, 2071 to 2102, 2170 to 2199 and 2270 to 2299 respectively.

is under review in the journal *Geophysical Research Letters*, that include contribution from the projects COMFORT, KeyCLIM and IMPOSE (co-authored by Heinze, Schwinger and Torsvik).

Task 7.4: Limits of irreversibility

In task 7.4 we synthesize and summarize how the collective effect of the numerous improved processes in NorESM shape our understanding of northern high latitude climate change under high emission scenarios. This task aims to quantify the limits of reversible climate change and how the enhanced NorESM provides a better answer to the key question: What is dangerous climate change and what emissions are compatible with avoiding it?

Arctic sea ice loss

NorESM2 was used to acquire a better understanding of the influence of sea-ice loss on Arctic warming using extended sets of coupled model experiments, part of the Polar Amplification Model Intercomparison Project (PAMIP) contributing to CMIP6. These experiments were identical except that they were nudged to present day and future sea-ice extent. By construction, the difference between the experiments provides the simulated climate response to future Arctic sea-ice loss in NorESM2. The results demonstrate Arctic warming with a pronounced seasonal cycle as a response to sea-ice reduction. The Arctic warming is most prominent during autumn and winter, with a maximum November warming above 6°C in the regions where sea-ice is retreating due to lower surface albedo during summer. Reduced albedo, cause more solar radiation to be absorbed by the upper ocean, increasing ocean heat storage. There is an increased air sea temperature gradient during the cold season as the relatively cold atmosphere is exposed to more open ocean, resulting in increased upward turbulent fluxes which moisten the atmosphere and increase the cloud cover, and subsequently contribute to increased downwelling longwave radiative flux which warms the Arctic surface. The warming is found to be dominated by regional processes, rather than large-scale transports, in line with e.g. Boeke and Taylor, 2018.

The Arctic climate change in a future scenario experiment, shared socioeconomic pathway 5-8.5 (SSP5-8.5), was compared to the nudged sea-ice experiments, when similar conditions of sea-ice extent was reached. This comparison reveal similar seasonal cycle of near-surface warming, albeit a smaller amplitude is seen in SSP5-8.5 and the large scale lateral transports are found to be instrumental.

Figure 7.3.3: Timeseries from ZECMIP B3 experiment extended run for (a) net downward CO₂ flux into the ocean, and (b) global averaged sea surface temperature.

(a) Surface Density

(b) Surface Ocean Current

(c) Atlantic Meridional Overturning Streamfunction

Figure 7.3.4: Changes in surface density (Kg/m^3) (a), ocean currents (cm/s) at the surface (b), and Atlantic meridional overturning streamfunction (Sv) (c). Contours show 1 Kg/m^3 and 10 Sv intervals in (a) and (c), respectively. The change is calculated by subtracting the control experiment 50-year means for each of the variable from the respective five-year means from the abrupt-4xCO₂ experiment. Year 1 is the year when CO₂ is abruptly quadrupled. Figure from Madan et al. 2023.

Interestingly, under strong GHG forcing (SSP5-8.5) there seem to be dampening effects on the seasonal warming cycle due to solely sea-ice loss. This study was carried out in Buraas' Master Thesis <https://www.duo.uio.no/handle/10852/97057> and a publication is planned in the near future.

AMOC weakening

The accelerated warming induced by anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) could trigger several climate tipping points, leading to irreversible climate impacts. The potential weakening or even collapse of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) stands out as a critical tipping point. This weakening has been investigated under extreme GHG forcing, specifically at four times the current atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration (abrupt-4xCO₂), utilizing data from 35 CMIP6 models, with a special focus on the response in NorESM2-LM. The intensified forcing induces enhanced Arctic warming, leading to the extensive melting of Arctic sea ice. The resulting tongue of freshwater which extends into the interior North Atlantic diminishes the density gradient along the separated Gulf Stream, known as the North Atlantic Current (Fig. 7.3.4 a)). This implies a weakening of the zonal velocity shear $\partial u/\partial z$, from the thermal wind relation, and hence a decrease in the surface velocities (Fig. 7.3.4 b)). Contrary to common perception, where freshwater is thought to cap convection regions and stifle deepwater production, these simulations reveal that it is the inflow to the subpolar gyre that is suppressed. Hence, an increase in freshwater discharge, particularly from the Labrador Sea, serves as the precursor to AMOC weakening in this scenario (Fig. 7.3.4 c)). This study was published in *Climate Dynamics* in September 2023 (Madan et al. 2023).

7.4 Deliverables

- **D7.1 Report on the impact of enhanced resolution and eddy parameterization:** (a specific report is in preparation, results are partly covered by D3.2 and D6.3)
- **D7.2 Publication on detection and quantification of climate-ice sheet feedbacks:** This publication is delayed due to personal reasons. However, all simulations have been completed successfully, the analysis is complete, and a draft manuscript is in near final form: Konstanze Haubner, Heiko Goelzer, Andreas Born, Petra Langebroek: Limited global effect of climate-Greenland ice sheet coupling in NorESM under a high-emission scenario, in preparation for JAMES - Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems
- **D7.3 Publ. on carbon chemistry changes with enhanced mixed layer (M54):** This objective was subject to difficulties in the development of the hybrid vertical coordinate scheme in BLOM (Task 3.1), which allowed for only a limited evaluation of ocean-only simulations. A decision was made to instead contribute to D7.4. A publication is currently in revision: C. Heinze, C. Michel, T. Torsvik, J. Schwinger, and J. F. Tjiputra: More frequent abrupt marine environmental changes expected, manuscript submitted to *Geophysical Research Letters*
- **D7.4 Synthesis publ. on future major and irreversible Earth system changes** (paper in preparation for *Climate Dynamics*: A Gjermundsen et al. "Irreversibility of climate properties in overshoot scenarios simulated by NorESM2 ")

WP8 Coordination of KeyCLIM

WP leaders: Michael Schulz (MET), Mats Bentsen (NORCE)

Contributing persons: Ada Gjermundsen (MET), Augustin Mortier (MET), Yanchun He (NERSC)

8.1 Main objectives and goals

The overarching goal of WP8 was to ensure an efficient KeyCLIM workflow and communication, to foster work across Earth system disciplines and to manage the project as a whole. The secondary goals were: (1) to communicate efficiently with the broader climate science community in Norway and internationally, (2) to initiate outreach activities for climate services, public and policy makers based on KeyCLIM science findings, and finally (3) coordinate project meetings, finances and reporting.

8.2 Major results

Task 8.1: Coordination of KeyCLIM workflow

The workflow in the project was maintained by a combination of biweekly virtual NorESM core meetings, WP leader meetings, dedicated coordination meetings and synthesis workshops. A project website is in place (keyclim.met.no) with contributions from all WPs, that contains an essential overview over the activities, data and publication results of the project. The model development in KeyCLIM has to a large degree been done in coordination and based on the Infrastructure for Norwegian Earth System modelling (INES). The different KeyCLIM model changes and upgrades were organised by the KeyCLIM consortium through the NorESM code hub (<https://github.com/NorESMhub/NorESM>). The hub contains a base and forks/branches containing code for the coordinated KeyCLIM sensitivity experiments, in particular those for WP6. Publication coordination has been largely done on WP level.

In the project several internal KeyCLIM workshops have been organized. We highlight:

- Four KeyCLIM annual meetings in Bergen and Oslo, each with 35 participants.
- Twenty regular almost monthly video conferences since 2020 on the state and analysis of the coordinated model experiments from WP6, including a synthesis workshop 1st of June 2022 and a follow up of that in June 2023.
- A KeyCLIM model update workshop (8th of March 2022). The goal of this workshop was to revisit the progress made on model improvements and plan and review spinup and historical simulations, and prepare associated analysis in WP6.

Task 8.2: Communication with Earth system science community

The discussion with the broader Earth system science community were done on several levels. Contributions to the international CMIP community were made e.g. by involvement in the formulation of a new core set of variables and experiments for climate models, based on experience from CMIP6. This work is coordinated by the new WCRP CMIP International Project Office in preparation of CMIP7. Partners were active to promote KeyCLIM science results in different working groups associated to several CMIP6 endorsed model intercomparison projects (AerChemMIP, RFMIP, C4MIP, CFMIP, DAMIP, PAMIP, CORDEX). Members of the KeyCLIM consortium are also active to shape the forthcoming CMIP7 model intercomparison framework by serving in steering bodies, contributing to discussions in MIPs and on WCRP/WMO level. KeyCLIM also initiated the exploratory use of the ESMvalTOOL, which has been developed for the wider ESM science community by the ESMvalTOOL community (<https://esmvaltool.org>) and was adapted and included into the NorESMhub (<https://github.com/NorESMhub/noresmvaltool>).

A KeyCLIM workshop with broader participation from the Earth System science community was held 22 - 23th of September 2022 with two hubs in Oslo and Bergen on "Constraining the large spread in 21st century climate projection". Despite continuous improvements in generations of Earth system models, large spread in projections of key climate metrics persist, highlighting the need to better understand the source of model spread. The workshop was organised together with the NFR COLUMBIA project. Different methodologies in assessing multi-model ensemble performance and constraining projection uncertainties were discussed. 16 researchers presented various approaches used to evaluate model performances and identify the root of the projections spread.

A second KeyCLIM workshop, reaching beyond the KeyCLIM partner community, was held 25th of May 2023 in Oslo on "Precipitation trends in Nordic regions". 30 participants participated representing experts from NFR projects BUDGET, ClimDesign, SamVann and KlimaDigital and the community around "Downscaling Norway". The focus was to review recent progress to predict future precipitation trends in the Nordic regions. Experts were invited to comment on eventually robust trends in observed precipitation parameters, the ability of models to reproduce them, the drivers of such trends (atmospheric rivers, warming, circulation changes, humidity trends, coupling with land and ocean), and the uncertainty in future predictions.

Task 8.3: Dissemination and Outreach

Specific dissemination presentations have been organized on latest KeyCLIM findings such as presentations by Ada Gjermundsen (Ocean Sciences Meeting, March 3, 2022 ; GFDL Journal Club, May 24,

2022; Arctic Forum, June 9, 2022 Tromsø; FORCeS annual meeting, September 15, 2022 Oslo), Michael Schulz (Presentation during visit by minister of Climate and Environment to MET Norway April 25, 2022; Invited presentation at the 3rd IPICS Open Science Conference in Crans-Montana, Switzerland, Oct 3, 2022). Recent work, showing the robust evidence of reductions in aerosol forcing and thus an additional climate warming contribution as side effect of air quality policies (Quaas et al. 2022) has led to articles in 5 Norwegian newspapers, including Aftenposten (Sept. 22, 2022).

The coordination of the project comprised different activities to foster exchange among WPs and scientists involved. A KeyCLIM twitter account has been made which is linked to the KeyCLIM web site; <https://twitter.com/KeyCLIMNFR>. A project website has been prepared and is in place (key-clim.met.no) with contributions from all WPs, that contains an essential overview over the activities, data and publication results of the project. The website is meant both for internal communication and for informing the wider climate science community.

Task 8.4: Financial administration and reporting

Financial reporting was regularly invoked with all partners. Since UNINETT Sigma2 provided most of the HPC and storage resources needed by KeyCLIM, WP8 has planned and monitored the resource use and applied to Sigma2 for CPU and storage resources.

8.3 Deliverables

- D8.1 Kick-off meeting of KeyCLIM; The kickoff meeting was held 16.5.2019
- D8.2 Annual KeyCLIM all-staff science meetings: Annual all staff meetings were held 5-6 Sep 2019 (Bergen), 25 Oct 2020 (virtual), 20 -21 Oct 2021 (Bergen) and 21-22 June 2023 (Oslo, hybrid).
- D8.3 Report on Nordic Earth system science conference (M33) The original plan to hold a larger conference in cooperation with Nordic partners could not be pursued due to COVID related difficulties. Instead, we held an open, inter-project workshop on "Constraining model uncertainty in climate sensitivity" in September 2022 with 30 Participants (at 2 hubs in Bergen and Oslo). The presentations were made available to all participants via the project google drive.
- D8.5 Report on communication activities in KeyCLIM as specified in dissemination plan. No specific report is done, as the activities over the whole project period have been assembled in this final report.

References

- Bock J, Michou M, Nabat P, Abe M, Mulcahy JP, Olivié DJL, Schwinger J, Suntharalingam P, Tjiputra J, van Hulst M, Watanabe M, Yool A, Séférian R (2021) Evaluation of ocean dimethylsulfide concentration and emission in cmip6 models. *Biogeosciences* 18(12):3823–3860, 10.5194/bg-18-3823-2021
- Boeke R, Taylor P (2018) Seasonal energy exchange in sea ice retreat regions contributes to differences in projected arctic warming. *Nature Communications* 9:5017, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07061-9>
- Conley AJ, Lamarque JF, Vitt F, Collins WD, Kiehl J (2013) Port, a cesm tool for the diagnosis of radiative forcing. *GMD* 6(2):469–476, 10.5194/gmd-6-469-2013
- Emmons LK, Schwantes RH, Orlando JJ, Tyndall G, Kinnison D, Lamarque JF, Marsh D, Mills MJ, Tilmes S, Bardeen C, Buchholz RR, Conley A, Gettelman A, Garcia R, Simpson I, Blake DR, Meinardi S, Pétron G (2020) The chemistry mechanism in the community earth system model version 2 (cesm2). *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 12(4):e2019MS001882, 10.1029/2019MS001882
- Eyring V, Bony S, Meehl GA, Senior CA, Stevens B, Stouffer RJ, Taylor KE (2016) Overview of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) experimental design and organization. *Geoscientific Model Development* 9(5):1937–1958, 10.5194/gmd-9-1937-2016
- Fox-Kemper B, Ferrari R, Hallberg R (2008) Parameterization of Mixed Layer Eddies. Part I: Theory and Diagnosis. *J Phys Oceanogr* 38:1145–1165

- Gent PR, McWilliams JC (1990) Isopycnal Mixing in Ocean Circulation Models. *J Phys Oceanogr* 20:150–155
- Gottelman A, Morrison H, Eidhammer T, Thayer-Calder K, Sun J, Forbes R, McGraw Z, Zhu J, Storelvmo T, Dennis J (2023) Importance of ice nucleation and precipitation on climate with the parameterization of unified microphysics across scales version 1 (pumasv1). *Geoscientific Model Development* 16(6):1735–1754, 10.5194/gmd-16-1735-2023
- Gjermundsen A, Nummelin A, Olivie D, Bentsen M, Seland Ø, Schulz M (2021) Shutdown of southern ocean convection controls long-term greenhouse gas-induced warming. *Nat Geosci* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-021-00825-x>
- Hagen JS, Leblois E, Lawrence D, Solomatine D, Sorteberg A (2021) Identifying major drivers of daily streamflow from large-scale atmospheric circulation with machine learning. *Journal of Hydrology* 596:126086, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126086>
- Hagen JS, Hasibi R, Leblois E, Lawrence D, Sorteberg A (2023) Reconstructing daily streamflow and floods from large-scale atmospheric variables with feed-forward and recurrent neural networks in high latitude climates. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 68(3):412–431, 10.1080/02626667.2023.2165927
- Hofer S, Hahn L, Shaw J, McGraw Z, Bruno O, Hellmuth F, Pietschnig M, Mostue I, David R, Carlsen T, Storelvmo T (2023) Realistic representation of cloud phase increases future warming. *Communications Earth and Environment* Accepted, 10.21203/rs.3.rs-2981113/v1
- Jia Y, Hahn J, Quack B, Jones E, Brehon M, Tegtmeier S (2023) Anthropogenic bromoform at the extratropical tropopause. *Geophysical Research Letters* 50(9):e2023GL102894, 10.1029/2023GL102894
- Karset IHH, Berntsen TK, Storelvmo T, Alterskjær K, Grini A, Olivie D, Kirkevåg A, Seland Ø, Iversen T, Schulz M (2018) Strong impacts on aerosol indirect effects from historical oxidant changes. *Atmos Chem Phys* 18(10):7669–7690, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-18-7669-2018>
- Large WG, McWilliams JC, Doney SC (1994) Oceanic vertical mixing: A review and a model with a nonlocal boundary layer parameterization. *Rev Geophys* 32(4):363–403, <https://doi.org/10.1029/94RG01872>
- Lauritzen PH, Kevlahan NKR, Toniazzo T, Eldred C, Dubos T, Gassmann A, Larson VE, Jablonowski C, Guba O, Shipway B, Harrop BE, Lemarié F, Tailleux R, Herrington AR, Large W, Rasch PJ, Donahue AS, Wan H, Conley A, Bacmeister JT (2022) Reconciling and improving formulations for thermodynamics and conservation principles in Earth System Models (ESMs). *J Adv Model Earth Syst* 14, {10.1029/2022MS003117}
- Loeb NG, Johnson GC, Thorsen TJ, Lyman JM, Rose FG, Kato S (2021) Satellite and ocean data reveal marked increase in earth's heating rate. *Geophys Res Lett* 48(13):e2021GL093047, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL093047>
- Lu J, Cai M (2009) A new framework for isolating individual feedback processes in coupled general circulation climate models. *Climate Dynamics* 32:873–885, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-008-0425-3>
- Madan G, Gjermundsen A, Iversen SC, LaCasce JH (2023) The weakening amoc under extreme climate change. *Clim Dyn* pp 1–19, 10.1007/s00382-023-06957-7
- McGraw Z, Storelvmo T, Samset BH, Stjern CW (2020) Global Radiative Impacts of Black Carbon Acting as Ice Nucleating Particles. *Geophysical Research Letters* 47(20):1–9, 10.1029/2020GL089056
- McGraw Z, Storelvmo T, Polvani L, Hofer S, Shaw J, Gottelman A (2023) On the Links Between Ice Nucleation, Cloud Phase, and Climate Sensitivity in CESM2. *Geophysical Research Letters* 50:e2023GL105053, 10.1029/2023GL105053
- Michel C, Sorteberg A, Eckhardt S, Weijenborg C, Stohl A, Cassiani M (2021) Characterization of the atmospheric environment during extreme precipitation events associated with atmospheric rivers in norway - seasonal and regional aspects. *Weather and Climate Extremes* 34:100370, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2021.100370>

- O'Neill BC, Tebaldi C, van Vuuren DP, Eyring V, Friedlingstein P, Hurtt G, Knutti R, Kriegler E, Lamarque JF, Lowe J, Meehl GA, Moss R, Riahi K, Sanderson BM (2016) The Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP) for CMIP6. *Geoscientific Model Development* 9(9):3461–3482, 10.5194/gmd-9-3461-2016
- Outten S, Davy R (2023) Changes in the north atlantic oscillation over the 20th century. *EGUsphere* 2023:1–13, 10.5194/egusphere-2023-2832
- Pendergrass AG, Conley A, Vitt FM (2018) Surface and top-of-atmosphere radiative feedback kernels for cesm-cam5. *Earth System Science Data* 10(1):317–324, 10.5194/essd-10-317-2018
- Pincus R, Forster PM, Stevens B (2016) The radiative forcing model intercomparison project (rfmip): experimental protocol for cmip6. *Geosci Model Dev* 9(9):3447–3460, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-3447-2016>
- Quaas J, Jia H, Smith C, Albright AL, Aas W, Bellouin N, Boucher O, Doutriaux-Boucher M, Forster PM, Grosvenor D, Jenkins S, Klimont Z, Loeb NG, Ma X, Naik V, Paulot F, Stier P, Wild M, Myhre G, Schulz M (2022) Robust evidence for reversal of the trend in aerosol effective climate forcing. *ACP* 22(18):12221–12239, 10.5194/acp-22-12221-2022
- Rantanen M, Karpechko AY, Lipponen A, Nordling K, Hyvärinen O, Ruosteenoja K, Vihma T, Laaksonen A (2022) The arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979. *Communications Earth & Environment* 3(1):1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3>
- Seland Ø, Bentsen M, Olivie D, Toniazzo T, Gjermundsen A, Graff LS, Debernard JB, Gupta AK, He YC, Kirkevåg A, Schwinger J, Tjiputra J, Aas KS, Bethke I, Fan Y, Griesfeller J, Grini A, Guo C, Ilicak M, Karset IHH, Landgren O, Liakka J, Moseid KO, Nummelin A, Spensberger C, Tang H, Zhang Z, Heinze C, Iversen T, Schulz M (2020) Overview of the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM2) and key climate response of CMIP6 DECK, historical, and scenario simulations. *Geoscientific Model Development* 13(12):6165–6200, 10.5194/gmd-13-6165-2020
- Shao AE, Adcroft A, Hallberg R, Griffies SM (2020) A General-Coordinate, Nonlocal Neutral Diffusion Operator. *J Adv Model Earth Syst* 12, {10.1029/2019MS001992}
- Shaw J, McGraw Z, Bruno O, Storelvmo T, Hofer S (2022) Using Satellite Observations to Evaluate Model Microphysical Representation of Arctic Mixed-Phase Clouds. *Geophysical Research Letters* 49(3):e2021GL096191, 10.1029/2021GL096191
- Shu Q, Wang Q, Guo C, Song Z, Wang S, He Y, Qiao F (2023) Arctic ocean simulations in the cmip6 ocean model intercomparison project (omip). *Geoscientific Model Development* 16:2539–2563, 10.5194/gmd-16-2539-2023
- Skeie RB, Myhre G, Hodnebrog Ø, Cameron-Smith PJ, Deushi M, Hegglin MI, Horowitz LW, Kramer RJ, Michou M, Mills MJ, et al. (2020) Historical total ozone radiative forcing derived from cmip6 simulations. *Npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* 3(1):32
- Smith C, Kramer R, Myhre G, Forster P, Soden B, Andrews T, Boucher O, Faluvegi G, Fläschner D, Hodnebrog Ø, et al. (2018) Understanding rapid adjustments to diverse forcing agents. *Geophys Res Lett* 45(21):12–023, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL079826>
- Smith C, Harris G, Palmer M, Bellouin N, Collins W, Myhre G, Schulz M, Golaz JC, Ringer M, Storelvmo T, et al. (2021) Energy budget constraints on the time history of aerosol forcing and climate sensitivity. *J Geophys Res Atmos* p e2020JD033622, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JD033622>
- Smith CJ, Kramer RJ, Myhre G, Alterskjær K, Collins W, Sima A, Boucher O, Dufresne JL, Nabat P, Michou M, et al. (2020a) Effective radiative forcing and adjustments in cmip6 models. *Atmos Chem Phys* 20(16):9591–9618, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-9591-2020>
- Smith CJ, Kramer RJ, Sima A (2020b) The hadgem3-ga7.1 radiative kernel: the importance of a well-resolved stratosphere. *Earth System Science Data* 12(3):2157–2168, 10.5194/essd-12-2157-2020
- Stemmler I, Hense I, Quack B (2015) Marine sources of bromoform in the global open ocean – global patterns and emissions. *Biogeosciences* 12(6):1967–1981, 10.5194/bg-12-1967-2015

- Thornhill G, Collins W, Olivie D, Skeie RB, Archibald A, Bauer S, Checa-Garcia R, Fiedler S, Folberth G, Gjermundsen A, Horowitz L, Lamarque JF, Michou M, Mulcahy J, Nabat P, Naik V, O'Connor FM, Paulot F, Schulz M, Scott CE, Séférian R, Smith C, Takemura T, Tilmes S, Tsigaridis K, Weber J (2021a) Climate-driven chemistry and aerosol feedbacks in cmip6 earth system models. *Atmos Chem Phys* 21(2):1105–1126, 10.5194/acp-21-1105-2021
- Thornhill GD, Collins WJ, Kramer RJ, Olivie D, Skeie RB, O'Connor FM, Abraham NL, Checa-Garcia R, Bauer SE, Deushi M, Emmons LK, Forster PM, Horowitz LW, Johnson B, Keeble J, Lamarque JF, Michou M, Mills MJ, Mulcahy JP, Myhre G, Nabat P, Naik V, Oshima N, Schulz M, Smith CJ, Takemura T, Tilmes S, Wu T, Zeng G, Zhang J (2021b) Effective radiative forcing from emissions of reactive gases and aerosols – a multi-model comparison. *Atmos Chem Phys* 21(2):853–874, 10.5194/acp-21-853-2021
- White L, Adcroft A (2008) A high-order finite volume remapping scheme for nonuniform grids: The piecewise quartic method (pqm). *J Comput Phys* 227(15):7394–7422, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2008.04.026>
- White L, Adcroft A, Hallberg R (2009) High-order regridding–remapping schemes for continuous isopycnal and generalized coordinates in ocean models. *J Comput Phys* 228(23):8665–8692, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2009.08.016>
- Yang M, Bell TG, Bidlot JR, Blomquist BW, Butterworth BJ, Dong Y, Fairall CW, Landwehr S, Marandino CA, Miller SD, Saltzman ES, Zavarisky A (2022) Global synthesis of air-sea co2 transfer velocity estimates from ship-based eddy covariance measurements. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 9, 10.3389/fmars.2022.826421
- Zelinka MD, Myers TA, McCoy DT, Po-Chedley S, Caldwell PM, Ceppi P, Klein SA, Taylor KE (2020) Causes of higher climate sensitivity in cmip6 models. *Geophys Res Lett* 47(1):e2019GL085782, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL085782>
- Zhu J, Otto-Bliesner BL, Brady EC, Gettelman A, Bacmeister JT, Neale RB, Poulsen CJ, Shaw JK, McGraw ZS, Kay JE (2022) LGM Paleoclimate Constraints Inform Cloud Parameterizations and Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity in CESM2. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 14(4):e2021MS002776, 10.1029/2021MS002776
- Ziska F, Quack B, Abrahamsson K, Archer SD, Atlas E, Bell T, Butler JH, Carpenter LJ, Jones CE, Harris NRP, Hepach H, Heumann KG, Hughes C, Kuss J, Krüger K, Liss P, Moore RM, Orlikowska A, Raimund S, Reeves CE, Reifenhäuser W, Robinson AD, Schall C, Tanhua T, Tegtmeier S, Turner S, Wang L, Wallace D, Williams J, Yamamoto H, Yvon-Lewis S, Yokouchi Y (2013) Global sea-to-air flux climatology for bromoform, dibromomethane and methyl iodide. *Atmos Chem Phys* 13(17):8915–8934, 10.5194/acp-13-8915-2013